

Expanding Integrated Assessment Modelling:
Comprehensive and Comprehensible Science
for Sustainable, Co-Created Climate Action

D6.3 – IAM COMPACT CDE plan – Update 2

WP6 – Explaining – Policy
analysis, capacity development,
communication, dissemination,
exploitation.

31/08/2025

The IAM COMPACT project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101056306.

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Grant Agreement Number	101056306		Acronym	IAM COMPACT	
Full Title	Expanding Integrated Assessment Modelling: Comprehensive and Comprehensible Science for Sustainable, Co-Created Climate Action				
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D1-01-04				
Funding scheme	HORIZON EUROPE, RIA – Research and Innovation Action				
Start Date	September 2022	Duration	36 Months		
Project URL	https://www.iam-compact.eu				
EU Project Advisor	Andreas Palialexis				
Project Coordinator	National Technical University of Athens – NTUA				
Deliverable	D6.3 – IAM COMPACT CDE plan – Update 2				
Work Package	WP6 – Explaining-Policy analysis, capacity development, communication, dissemination, exploitation				
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/08/2025	Actual	31/08/2025	
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public		
Lead Beneficiary	University of Piraeus Research Center (UPRC)				
Responsible Author	Sophia Theodoropoulou	Email	stheodor@unipi.gr		
	UPRC	Phone	+30 210 414 2017		
Contributors	Vassilis Stavrakas [UPRC]				
Reviewer(s)	Christina Tigka, Anastasios Karamaneas, Natasha Frilingou, Alexandros Nikas [NTUA]				
Keywords	Communication Plan, Dissemination Plan, Exploitation Strategy				

EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable presents the second and final update to the IAM COMPACT Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) Plan, originally developed in Month 6 (M6) to set out the forward-looking strategy to be followed for maximising the project's visibility and ensuring that its scientific outputs remain accessible, relevant, and embedded in future policy and modelling efforts. It reviews the activities implemented since then and assesses their performance against a set of predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). Accordingly, this final update captures the whole-project performance and aligns outcomes with the project's long-term objectives, pointing to how IAM COMPACT's research contributions can be sustained and scaled in the future.

In summary, its purpose is to offer an evidence-based account for the consortium partners of the overall effectiveness of the implemented CDE strategy, reflecting on what worked well and how it had evolved over time. Beyond that, the deliverable can be used as a documentation of the IAM COMPACT outreach effort across the three pillars of the CDE plan - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation - and/or as a reference framework that could inform similar efforts of other research teams and projects working also at the science-policy interface.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

This deliverable offers the final update to the IAM COMPACT Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) Plan, outlining the full scope and results of the project's outreach strategy. Building on the foundations laid in the initial¹ and first updated² versions, it captures the efforts made to ensure that the IAM COMPACT project's research outputs—including models, tools, insights, policy recommendations—reached relevant audiences and supported meaningful uptake at local, national, and international levels.

Over the course of the project, the CDE plan evolved from a forward-looking into a fully operational strategy. It guided focused communication, encouraged knowledge exchange, and supported capacity building, particularly in the project's four pilot countries, Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine. Driven by a co-creative approach, it enabled active stakeholder participation and promoted the alignment of scientific work with real-world policy needs and priorities.

This final update evaluates the whole-project CDE implementation strategy against 11 predefined performance indicators and long-term output and impact expectations. It offers an account of what was achieved, how tools and approaches were adapted and refined, and where the greatest added value was delivered. As such, it is both a final report and a reference point for similar research initiatives seeking to strengthen the interface between integrated assessment modelling, policymaking, and society.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

¹ D6.1 - IAM COMPACT CDE plan (D6.1) [\[link\]](#)

² D6.2 - IAM COMPACT CDE plan - Update 1 (D6.2) [\[link\]](#)

Preface

IAM COMPACT supports the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, and the design of the next round of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and policy planning beyond 2030 for major emitters and non-high-income countries. It uses a diverse ensemble of models, tools, and insights from social and political sciences and operations research, integrating bodies of knowledge to co-create the research process and enhance transparency, robustness, and policy relevance. It explores the role of structural changes in major emitting sectors and of political, behaviour, and social aspects in mitigation, quantifies factors promoting or hindering climate neutrality, and accounts for extreme scenarios, to deliver a range of global and national pathways that are environmentally effective, viable, feasible, and desirable. In doing so, it fully accounts for COVID-19 impacts and recovery strategies and aligns climate action with broader sustainability goals, while developing technical capacity and promoting ownership in non-high-income countries.

NTUA – National Technical University of Athens	EL	
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AAU – Aalborg Universitet	DK	
BC3 – Asociacion BC3 Basque Centre for Climate Change – Klima Aldaketa Ikergai	ES	
Bruegel – Bruegel AISBL	BE	
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CICERO – Cicero Senter for Klimaforskning Stiftelse	NO	
E3M – E3-Modelling AE	EL	
KTH – Kungliga Tekniska Hoegskolan	SE	
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UPRC – University of Piraeus Research Center	EL	
UVa – Universidad De Valladolid	ES	
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IIMA – Indian Institute of Management	IN	
THU – Tsinghua University	CN	
USMF – University System of Maryland	US	
AAiT – Addis Ababa University	ET	
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RUSL – Raja Rata University of Sri Lanka	LK	
TUM – Technical University of Mombasa	KE	
UNIGE – Université de Genève	CH	
Imperial – Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine	UK	

Executive Summary

In a time of accelerating climate urgency, IAM COMPACT set out to support the design of more ambitious and evidence-based Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and long-term strategies, especially in major emitting and non-high-income countries across Europe and beyond. Recognising the need for robust and policy-relevant modelling tools, the project embedded a participatory and co-creative research approach to introduce a novel demand-driven, multi-dimensional framework aimed at advancing Integrated Assessment Modelling (IAM). Through this path, the project sought to strengthen the policy relevance of its modelling outputs, ensuring that they were both scientifically sound and reflected real-world policy priorities.

To drive this process, two innovative tools, the Policy Response Mechanism (PRM) and the upgraded IAM PARIS platform, were designed to turn stakeholder-driven analyses into actionable and impactful guidance for the EU and international climate policy. In parallel, the IAM COMPACT CDE plan—designed to enable these outputs to reach the right audiences and remain useful beyond the project’s funding period—played a critical role.

This report, Deliverable D6.3 (*'IAM COMPACT CDE Plan - Update 2'*), presents the final update to the project’s structured effort to identify and activate those levers that would increase the visibility of IAM COMPACT on selected target audiences, from local to European and broader levels, and to promote its long-term sustainability and scalability upon the project’s finalisation. Therefore, the focus of this report lies on the project’s entire CDE journey, reviewed and assessed in terms of both its performance through 11 predefined success indicators, and its progress towards the project’s long-term expectations. In doing so, our overview captures the breadth of the CDE activities planned and carried out to date, reflecting also the depth of their integration into the project’s overarching mission to generate meaningful, lasting impact across various scientific, societal, and policy domains.

Specifically, these ranged from standard public-facing activities (e.g., promotional material, newsletters/press releases, blog posts and media articles, etc.) supported by a strong use of online communication channels (such as the project’s website and social media channels) to more focused scientific outreach, through peer-reviewed publications and contributions in high-impact conferences. They also involved a set of dynamic and engaging/inclusive procedures, namely a series of capacity development activities in the four case study countries (Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine) that alongside the PRM and the IAM PARIS platform facilitated the co-creation of the research process. A key result of these efforts was a set of policy briefs delivered to inform climate-related policy choices, with the IAM COMPACT project’s influence expanding well into the future.

Overall, the designed CDE plan proved effective in amplifying the project’s research work, enabling it to have real-word impact. As a cross-cutting effort under Work Package 6 (Explaining), it ensured that the project’s communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy was not handled as simply an add-on, but as a strategically integrated activity towards maximising the visibility and practical value of all project outputs within future policy and modelling landscapes. Additionally, as the project concludes, we are confident that its legacy includes a proven and adaptable CDE approach that can contribute to different projects’ ambition to stand at the intersection of science, policy, and society, and deliver robust, science-based policy advice.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Description
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution License
CCG	Climate Compatible Growth
CDE	Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation
CINEA	The European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CO₂	Carbon dioxide
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ECEMF	European Climate & Energy Modeling Forum
EMF	Energy Modeling Forum
EI	Expected Impacts
EMP-E	Energy Modelling Platform for Europe
EO	Expected Outcomes
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GST	Global Stocktake
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
IAMs	Integrated Assessment Models
IAMC	Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium
IEA-WEO	International Energy Agency-World Energy Outlook
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
AR7	7 th Assessment Report of the IPCC
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
M	Month
M.A.T	Messages, Audience, Tools
NDCs	Nationally Determined Contributions
Openmod	Open Energy Modelling Initiative
PRM	Policy Response Mechanism
R&I	Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SHs	Stakeholders
SSH	Social sciences and humanities
SoMe	Social media
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

Over its 36-month implementation period, IAM COMPACT sought to serve as a dynamic multidisciplinary interface bridging model-based research, informed policymaking, and societal dialogue in response to the growing demand for effective, inclusive, and sustainable climate solutions. Funded by the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE programme, the project developed a demand-driven, multi-layered Integrated Assessment Modelling (IAM) framework to support the design of the next-round Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and climate policy planning beyond 2030 - particularly in major emitting and non-high-income countries.

From the outset, the project's applied approach is rooted in inclusivity and co-creation, reflecting its strong commitment to delivering robust, science-based policy advice driven by stakeholder input. Driving this effort were two key IAM COMPACT novelties. First, the Policy Response Mechanism (PRM), a participatory framework designed to bring qualified stakeholders from various backgrounds into every stage of the research process—from scoping relevant policy questions to guiding and validating the key priorities and directions of the IAM COMPACT modelling work. Second, the IAM PARIS (prev. I²AM PARIS) open-access platform for climate and energy policy modelling, designed and later enhanced to serve as a Europe-wide and broader authoritative digital source for the diverse ensemble of national and global IAMs, energy system models, and sectoral models that were used in the project. Together, these two tools encouraged transparent access, knowledge exchange, and collaboration around our modelling results, thereby promoting a broad engagement with the project's research agenda.

In this light, a critical consideration for IAM COMPACT was to identify the specific "lever" that should be activated to render research outcomes relevant to various end-users and how to unlock this potential. Initially, this shaped the core objectives of the project's CDE plan: identifying the right audiences, when and how to interact with them, and what are the optimal approaches to ensure effective outreach. In turn, it led up to actionable roadmaps for the CDE implementation, indicating how to progressively maximise efforts, shifting from awareness-raising to enabling the widespread uptake and sustained impact of the project's scientifically significant outputs. This report marks the final update of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan and, as such, delivers a thorough overview of its performance to date.

1.1 Objective and scope of the deliverable

The IAM COMPACT CDE plan, a key output of Work Package 6 (WP6) within the "Explaining" component of the project, serves as a strategic cross-cutting framework that enhances the integration of outreach activities across the entire project structure, ensuring that all IAM COMPACT's outcomes are communicated and promoted as effectively as possible. Throughout its length, its successful roll out relied on the active support of all IAM COMPACT partners, whose role-specific contributions helped ensure consistent and well-informed CDE actions at all points in the project lifecycle.

As a strategic CDE milestone, this deliverable outlines the forward-looking strategy adopted to guide our effort towards maximising the visibility of IAM COMPACT and ensuring that its scientific outputs, knowledge, tools, and insights, will remain accessible, impactful, and embedded in future policy and modelling contexts. By doing so, it offers a full account of the activities carried out in that regard and assesses their effectiveness with particular focus on how they were implemented and/or refined in response to key learning over time. Accordingly, it provides a comprehensive evaluation of the CDE progress to date, measured against the project's set performance indicators and its long-term goals, pointing to how IAM COMPACT's research contributions can be sustained and scaled beyond the project's lifetime.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

Apart from this introductory part, the rest of the deliverable is organised into five subsequent sections. Section 2 briefly outlines the conceptual framework underpinning the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, while Section 3 assesses its advancement against the set KPIs and presents its contribution to the project's Expected Outputs (EO) and Impact (EI). Next is Section 3 which covers the project's CDE strategy and the execution of its planned activities across three strategic CDE pillars: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation. Finally, Sections 5 and 6 set out the operational guidelines governing the IAM COMPACT's CDE effort and list potential related risks alongside their corresponding mitigation measures in accordance with the Grant Agreement (GA), respectively.

The document concludes with a summary review of how the IAM COMPACT CDE plan was implemented throughout the project's length, with final remarks on its performance and future outlook.

2 The IAM COMPACT CDE plan

The IAM COMPACT Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) Plan was developed from the project's outset to provide a clear and systematic approach to communicating the project's goals, disseminating its outcomes and ensuring its lasting impact. Our intention was to build a strategic framework for coordinating the delivery of the different planned CDE activities both during and beyond the project's duration. As such, the IAM COMPACT CDE Plan served as a periodically updated core document that specified a set of guiding principles, a phased implementation timeline, well-defined responsibilities across partners, and a targeted mix of audience-specific tools and dissemination channels to promote the broader adoption and sustainable exploitation of the IAM COMPACT's methodological novelties and policy-relevant findings throughout the project's lifetime.

From its inception, the IAM COMPACT CDE Plan aligned with the project's stakeholder engagement approach³, which focused on involving a broad spectrum of actors who would shape and benefit from the project activities. By meeting the needs of each target audience group and promoting a two-way communication of the project's main results, our CDE strategy was geared towards strengthening both scientific rigour and societal impact.

This section briefly outlines the methodological framework underpinning the IAM COMPACT CDE Plan, providing an overview of its structure and strategic orientation. It summarises the key messages that formed the conceptual basis and guided the project's outreach efforts, and provides high-level information on the stakeholder mapping exercises that eventually informed the selection and use of targeted communication tools and channels, and the implementation procedures that contributed to established CDE KPIs and long-term EOs and EIs.

Full methodological documentation is available on [Deliverable D6.2 - IAM COMPACT CDE plan \(Update 1\)](#).

2.1 The IAM COMPACT CDE strategic framework and guiding principles

The IAM COMPACT CDE strategy was meticulously designed to enhance the visibility, accessibility, and long-term sustainability of the project's outcomes for a broad spectrum of target audiences, encompassing both scientific and non-scientific stakeholders. At its core lies the **M.A.T.** technique, a methodological approach for ensuring coherence between the:

- **M**essages (What information needs to be communicated and why it matters)
- **A**udience (Whom this information is intended for)
- **T**ools (How this information needs to be delivered)

In other words, an audience-focused framework designed to ensure that all messages are effectively delivered and meaningfully received by each stakeholder group through the most appropriate tools and channels, thereby maximising their relevance, resonance, and impact. Central to this framework are six core principles that run through every aspect of the IAM COMPACT's CDE strategy, ensuring that our CDE outputs were all: (i) accessible, (ii) actionable, (iii) credible and trusted, (iv) relevant, (v) timely, and (vi) easy to understand.

Over the full duration of IAM COMPACT, the CDE Plan consistently sought to embed these principles across all activities and the wide range of tools and channels used for CDE purposes - whether through social media, web-based fact sheets, feature stories, commentaries, infographics, newsletters, press releases, videos, or broader outreach and visibility efforts. The ultimate goal was to deliver content that informs, engages, and inspires trust across scientific, policy, and societal audiences.

To operationalise this, five guiding questions - **What, Why, Who, When, and How** - underpinned the IAM COMPACT CDE strategic planning, providing a solid basis for mapping out a coherent series of activities that not

³ Further information on the stakeholder engagement strategy and activities can be found in Deliverable 2.1 - Stakeholder Engagement Plan (D2.1), available [here](#).

only kept the whole effort on track with the project's evolving priorities, but also 'added up' to meet the target audiences' objectives. This made it possible for all scheduled actions to remain purposeful and result-oriented, thereby maximising their relevance, resonance, and impact for all target groups over the long term.

2.2 What made it work: The IAM COMPACT's CDE building blocks

The IAM COMPACT CDE strategy and plan rested on five interlocking building blocks, further elaborated in the following sub-sections, which provided the strategic scaffolding for translating the core project objectives into clear audience-specific messages and, ultimately, into meaningful CDE activities - delivered to diverse stakeholder groups at the appropriate time, through the most effective tools. Together, these building blocks served the goal of bringing visibility and raising awareness of the project itself, its themes and the challenges it addresses, also ensuring that the research findings reach key stakeholders in a targeted way. In doing so, they paved the way for their future uptake and impact across scientific, policy, and societal spheres.

2.2.1 Messages (What/Why)

A key building block is a clearly articulated narrative anchored in eight high-level messages⁴ reflecting the project's thematic priorities and ambition to address some of the most pressing challenges and opportunities in the climate-economy modelling landscape, including:

- Strengthening ambition and ownership of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs);
- Embedding co-creation and stakeholder knowledge in modelling frameworks;
- Building capacity in non high-income countries;
- Integrating demand-side transformations and behavioural change;
- Accounting for uncertainty, shocks, and transition risks;
- Mainstreaming sustainability and co-benefits into climate policy;
- Advancing interdisciplinary modelling;
- Using real-world policy baselines for robust pathway assessments.

Since the early stages of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, each of the messages was strategically linked to one or more of the four overarching CDE objectives:

1. **Raising awareness** of the project's vision, tools, and results.
2. **Generating understanding** of complex climate-economic modelling concepts and insights.
3. **Engaging stakeholders** in the co-creation, validation and application of the project's outcomes.
4. **Ensuring impact** by promoting the real-world uptake and exploitation of the research findings.

Figure 1. The IAM COMPACT CDE goals.

⁴ These messages, along with their main derivatives and the CDE-related objectives are presented in [Table 20](#) - Annex 1.

Beyond reinforcing consistency and coherence across all CDE efforts, this exercise served a deeper purpose: It helped crystallise and amplify IAM COMPACT’s mission to transform integrated assessment modelling into a policy-responsive and stakeholder-informed tool, making this mandate more visible and relatable to a wider network of stakeholders, particularly among modelling teams and policy-relevant audiences. This enabled the project to advance its goal of building public trust, consent, and support for evidence-based climate-related decision-making.

2.2.2 Audience (Who)

The second building block of the IAM COMPACT CDE approach rested on the in-depth understanding of what drives the different stakeholder groups— an insight that enabled the project to design CDE activities that invited engagement and participation on equal footing throughout its lifecycle. At the heart of this approach was the commitment to a meaningful two-way dialogue with the broad spectrum of target stakeholders, ensuring that they all had the opportunity to shape the research process alongside project partners, based on their distinct interests and levels of motivation or influence.

Depending on that, the project distinguished between internal stakeholders - including the consortium partners across 19 countries, the Scientific Advisory Board, and members of the European Commission directly involved in the project, such as the Project Officer - and external audiences, which were identified early in the project, including the following groups:

- Policymakers and negotiators from countries and regions represented in the consortium, actively involved in project co-creation activities through the Policy Response Mechanism (PRM). This group includes relevant actors from:
 - All EU Member States and relevant European Commission bodies not directly part of the consortium,
 - Other European countries such as the UK, Norway, and Switzerland,
 - The world’s top three emitters— China, the USA, and India,
 - Selected non-high-income countries with limited institutional capacity to support climate pledges using modelling tools, including the four pilot countries: Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine.
- Policymakers and negotiators from other major emitting countries (e.g., Indonesia, Japan, Canada) and additional non-high-income countries, for which national mitigation pathways for the post-2030 period will be developed to support evidence-based policy planning.
- Scientists, researchers, and academia, including (but not limited to):
 - Integrated assessment and energy system modellers,
 - Social scientists and interdisciplinary researchers,
 - Contributors to IPCC processes,
 - Researchers involved in relevant Horizon Europe and other EU-funded projects,
- Modelling and research communities, including (but not limited to):
 - IAMC, EMP-E, EMF, Openmod, OpTIMUS, ECEMF
 - Climate Compatible Growth (CCG)
 - RedMentes, Sustainability Transitions Research Network
- Industry and business actors, particularly from high-emitting or energy-intensive sectors.
- Civil society and citizens, including:
 - NGOs, climate advocacy groups, grassroots movements,
 - General public and community actors.
- Press and media stakeholders, such as:
 - Specialised energy/climate journals
 - General press and media outlets

Acknowledging that different stakeholder groups hold varying levels of interest in the project and influence over its outcomes, IAM COMPACT used a Power/Interest Grid to classify them into four engagement levels, ranging from the lowest (“monitor”), through two middle levels (“keep satisfied” and “keep informed”), to the highest (“manage closely”). This classification enabled proportionate and effective interaction throughout the project lifecycle, helping identify the specific stages of the CDE process where each group could contribute most meaningfully based on their relevance (interest) to the project and its research findings, and their ability to shape its impact (power).

[Table 1](#) below captures how and where the identified stakeholder groups fit into the CDE puzzle - reflecting their positioning in the Power/Interest Grid. For a closer look at the overall approach taken, see [Deliverable D6.2 - IAM COMPACT CDE plan \(Update 1\)](#).

Table 1. Roles of key stakeholder groups in the CDE activities

Stakeholder groups	Enhance IAM COMPACT visibility	Give feedback on IAM COMPACT outputs	Create exploitation opportunities	Foster collaboration
Internal Stakeholders				
IAM COMPACT consortium	√		√	√
Scientific Advisory Board		√	√	√
European Commission	√	√	√	
External Stakeholders				
Policymakers and negotiators from countries/regions represented in the consortium		√		√
Policymakers and negotiators from selected non-high-income countries represented in the consortium		√		√
Policymakers and Negotiators from other major emitters and non-high-income countries			√	√
Modelling researchers		√	√	√
Researchers in relevant EU projects	√	√	√	√
Scientists in IPCC and relevant processes		√	√	√
Social scientists		√	√	√
Academia	√	√	√	
Civil society, including civil society organisations and climate activist groups	√			√
Citizens	√			
Specialised press and media	√		√	
General press and media	√			

2.2.3 Tools (How)

The third building block of the IAM COMPACT CDE strategy revolves around the deployment of a diverse and varied portfolio of CDE tools and activities, carefully selected to suit the evolving maturity of the project outputs, the specific needs of different stakeholder groups, and the nature of interaction expected and/or required each time - informative, participatory, and/or action-oriented. To this end, IAM COMPACT employed a multi-channel approach, using both digital and physical formats to maximise coverage and impact. In brief⁵, it included:

- Core communication materials: flyers, roll-ups, factsheets, infographics, and project-branded templates.
- Digital platforms: the IAM COMPACT website, the interactive IAM PARIS (former I²AM PARIS) modelling platform, and dedicated social media channels.
- Scientific and policy dissemination: peer-reviewed publications (prioritising open-access), scientific conferences, and policy outputs.
- Engagement mechanisms and activities: the Policy Response Mechanism (PRM), stakeholder dialogues and co-creation workshops, webinars, policy events and other relevant activities as appropriate.
- Visibility and outreach tools: newsletters and press releases, public-facing articles, commentaries and blog posts, and videos aimed to broader audiences.
- Learning and capacity-building resources and activities: open-access training material and participatory workshops for long-term stakeholder modelling capacity empowerment, particularly in pilot and other non-high-income countries.

Together, these tools served as the operational armoury of the CDE strategy, supporting a different purpose and level of outreach. Key factors we considered when prioritising channels included their reach (audience size), recall (message retention), and impact (likelihood to prompt an expected action). By strategically combining high-exposure channels and repeating key messages, the IAM COMPACT gave its core messages the visibility and traction they needed to make a lasting impact.

2.2.4 Implementation agenda (When)

The fourth building block of the IAM COMPACT CDE strategy is its implementation agenda⁶, structured to ensure smooth coordination with the general project timeline and work plan. This breaks down into three phases - a six-month preparatory phase, followed by the two PRM co-creative modelling cycles, each of which marked an individual stage in the CDE journey:

- Communication (Months 1-36) laid the groundwork for getting the project in front of its priority audiences through early awareness-raising and targeted outreach activities.
- Dissemination (Months 7-36) continued and expanded on this momentum by delivering focused content, facilitating meaningful knowledge transfer, and deepening dialogue with key stakeholders around IAM COMPACT's accomplished developments.
- Exploitation (Months 22-36) set the stage for the IAM COMPACT's long-term legacy by supporting the future take-up and impact of the project's scientific findings, models, and tools on real-world policy and planning processes - making sure that they would continue to inform and influence climate decision-making long after the project's lifetime.

This phased yet embedded roll out allowed our CDE planning to unfold with strategic precision: timed to match the project's implementation rhythm, purpose-driven, and fully attuned to the needs of its stakeholder landscape. Rather than operating in silos, planned activities were interwoven with the IAM COMPACT's five methodological

⁵ [Table 21](#) - Annex 1 provides a comprehensive overview of the full suite of the IAMCOMPACT CDE tools, mapping which are most likely to be more effective for each audience. Further details are presented in the subsequent parts of this report.

⁶ The implementation agenda of the CDE plan can be found in [Table 22](#) - Annex 1.

pillars (“Listening”, “Exchanging”, “Modelling”, “Expanding”, and “Explaining”), cutting across the full range of the corresponding work packages (WPs 2–6). This approach upheld consistency and full alignment with the project’s research and scientific inquiries, the co-creation processes, and the engagement efforts every step of the way.

2.2.5 Monitoring

The monitoring approach followed to track progress of our CDE effort is the fifth and final building block, rounding out the IAM COMPACT’s CDE strategic framework. Built around 11 leading indicators, each tied to a core CDE activity, the applied structure enabled an ongoing feedback loop against specific benchmarks for success, making it possible to assess how well our CDE planning performed along the project’s implementation path, and to inform timely adjustments wherever gaps or areas in need of corrective action were spotted. This allowed for the CDE agenda to remain strategically aligned to the project’s priorities and impactful over time, ensuring that no critical issue was left unaddressed.

After the first CDE report⁷, which focused on the design and early execution of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, the monitoring process unfolded over two subsequent cycles in line with two project checkpoints:

- The mid-term reporting period (up to M18), which informed the first update of the CDE plan⁸ that looked into its performance status during the first half of the project.
- The final reporting period (up to M36), which led to this concluding CDE report that offers a thorough wrap-up and insights on the entire CDE journey.

Systematic data collection and reporting for all CDE-related activities, were enabled by an Excel-based CDE monitoring tool, developed and administered by the CDE plan leader (UPRC). Throughout the project duration, the tool served as the central repository for all relevant project-level data, offering built-in analysis and visualisation of the CDE performance across all priority actions and benchmarks.

To further ensure timely and coordinated documentation of the CDE effort, project partners were invited to offer regular input on their outreach activities (at least bi-monthly), using a simplified Excel template developed for that purpose. Contribution was optional and asked with flexibility in mind to accommodate different commitments and individual work plans.

Both tools were made available via the project’s internal communication platform, keeping the consortium up to date on the CDE progress at every stage, so promoting openness and shared oversight. In that way, they served as more than simple performance-tracking mechanisms; They provided a structured means to enhance strategic coherence of the IAM COMPACT’s outreach effort, upholding transparency and trustworthiness in all CDE outcomes.

⁷ The first CDE report, delivered in M6, is documented in [Deliverable D6.1 – The IAM COMPACT CDE plan](#).

⁸ The CDE plan’s first formal update was submitted as part of [Deliverable D6.2 - IAM COMPACT CDE plan \(Update 1\)](#).

3 Expected outcomes and impact: The CDE contribution

From its inception onwards, IAM COMPACT sought to contribute to the expected outcomes of the HORIZON CL5-2021-D1-01-04 call (EO), as well as the long-term expected impacts (EI) of the broader D1: Destination to support the transition to a climate-neutral and resilient society and economy enabled through advanced climate science, pathways, and responses to climate change (mitigation and adaptation), and behavioural transformations. These key outputs are presented in [Table 2](#) below and include:

Table 2. Expected outcomes and impacts.

IAM COMPACT's EOs		IAM COMPACT's EIs	
EO1	Provision of information for the preparation of climate policies and national planning for the post-2030 period, in light of the Paris Agreement goals and the need to reduce global net greenhouse emissions to zero by 2050.	EI1	Advancing knowledge and providing solutions in earth system science, pathways to climate neutrality, social science for climate action and better understanding of climate-ecosystems interactions.
EO2	Enhanced international cooperation among the modelling community and other relevant stakeholders to expand the provision of robust in-country advice to decision-makers around the world.	EI2	Contributing substantially to key international assessments.
EO3	Enhanced mutual learning among the modelling, social science, and policy communities to ensure coherence between different tools used to inform climate action, and consistency with the best available and open science.	EI3	Strengthening the European Research Area on climate change.
		EI4	Increasing the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness, and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate change for use by policymakers, practitioners, other stakeholders, and citizens.

The KPI framework embedded in the IAM COMPACT CDE plan functions as the roadmap for the project delivering on these ambitions with clarity, accountability, and purpose.

3.1 The KPI framework behind the CDE plan

Designed at the very beginning of the project, the CDE KPI framework was intended to turn IAM COMPACT's outreach ambitions into clear and trackable outcomes with lasting impact. Each of these is guided by concrete actions that drive progress across the three core pillars of the project's CDE strategy: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation.

This section presents how IAM COMPACT advanced toward meeting these standards of achievement over its full implementation timeline. [Table 3](#) below provides a snapshot of this progress, mapping it against the 11 leading performance indicators used to steer and measure the impact of our CDE strategy.

Table 3. CDE key performance indicators

Activity	Objectives	Audience	Monitoring Tool	CDE Indicator	Planned>	Achieved
IAM COMPACT visual identity	Creating distinctiveness and appeal of the project.	All SHs groups	Summary of all monitoring means			✓
Enhanced IAM PARIS platform & model documentation	Facilitating harmonisation of data & modelling. Fostering stakeholder co-creation of modelling assumptions, parameters & scenarios.	Policy, industry, academia	Google Analytics; GitHub metrics (viewers, forks, etc.)	Unique users/year	3,000	16,000
				Return of visitors	40%	17%
				Bounce rate	<50%	60%
Project website	Aiming to present and disseminate the project's results as well as to be a referenced source with	All SHs groups	Google Analytics (set up when the website launched)	Unique users/year	3,000	39,000
				Return of visitors	40%	8%
				Bounce rate	<50%	27%

Activity	Objectives	Audience	Monitoring Tool	CDE Indicator	Planned>	Achieved
	useful material and links related to the climate debate.					
Commentaries, briefs, newsletters (monthly)	Creating awareness and informing stakeholders on progress; reports and commentaries of policy interest.	All SHs groups	Email monitoring system; Website download analytics	No. of recipients/downloads	4,000	3,506
				Opening rate	30%	52%
Social Media channels	Creating awareness and familiarity with the project topic, objectives, results among policymakers, citizens, scientists & other groups.	All SHs groups	LinkedIn analytics	#iamcompact use on SoMe	1,000	1,160
				LinkedIn followers	500	1,248
Infographics & Videos	Creating awareness and familiarity with project objectives & results (especially among non-experts).	Civil society, policymakers	YouTube/Instagram statistics; No. of downloads	Videos views	1,500	5,192
				Infographics downloads/views	400	849
Open access self-learning training material	All the training material developed in Task 6.5 is publicly available & used in case-study countries and by stakeholders.	Young modelling teams	Google Analytics	Downloads/training kit	100	920
Blog posts, press releases, articles on news sites	Articles on climate, energy, environment, biodiversity, sustainability in leading news/media websites/blogs.	Civil society	Media monitoring; Copies of articles shared on the website	No. of articles/press releases	15	27 (link)
Networking activities with EU projects under the same or relevant topics	Creating awareness of the project and sharing results among the energy research, social science, modelling communities.	Academia	Digital monitoring; No. of joint papers & acknowledged projects in papers	No. of references in relevant projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers & project meetings	20	56
A final EU conference	Sharing the final project results.	All SHs groups	No. of attendees; minutes; photos	Audience (70-100)	70	>154
Scientific Outreach	Academic dissemination of the project's results (open access).	Academia	Digital monitoring	No. of papers	35	55 (link)
				No. of conferences	30	50 (link)

3.2 Shaping the future through measurable outcomes

The IAM COMPACT's vision extends beyond its immediate CDE KPI targets, reflecting the project's commitment to shaping long-term, measurable results with enduring policy and societal relevance. For that purpose, a forward-looking monitoring system was embedded into the IAM COMPACT CDE plan from the very beginning, for tracking progress of all relevant activities as the project's key exploitable achievements unfolded.

With most of its indicators designed to mature by or following the project's conclusion, this system ensured that steps were grounded in evidence and strategically oriented toward meaningful and impactful, future-oriented outcomes. Table 4 that follows presents the progress made to this point against these performance benchmarks.

Table 4. Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact.

EO# / EI#	Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact	Planned >	Achieved	Audience
Uptake by countries				
EO1	Long-term mitigation pathways and advice for the EU and countries represented in IAM COMPACT (top 3 emitters, four non-high-income countries)	8	Dozens (<i>see WP4, WP5 deliverables</i>)	Policymakers.
EI1	Countries within and outside Europe acknowledging the project in the development of national energy and climate action plans.	10	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
EI1	Top major emitters publishing NDCs based on evidence co-developed with stakeholders within IAM COMPACT.	4	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
EI1	Non-high-income countries publishing NDCs based on evidence co-developed with stakeholders in IAM COMPACT.	4	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
Project acknowledgement				
EO2	No. of citations of the advancements for expanded integrated assessment modelling capabilities.	100	<p><i>Although this is too early to assess, as of Aug 2025, papers acknowledging IAM COMPACT already have 96 citations:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sognnaes et al., 2022 (6) - Gambhir and Lempert, 2022 (6) - Giarola et al., 2023 (2) - McGoekin et al., 2024 (28) - Rodés-Bachs et al., 2024 (1) - Li et al., 2024 (6) - Calcaterra et al., 2024 (35) - Millot et al., 2010 (10) - Kleanthis et al., 2025 (2) 	Scientific community, IAM community.
EO2	No. of citations of the new set of diagnostics/evaluation indicators and protocols for model validation and integration published & used widely in modelling research	50	<p><i>Although this is too early to assess, as of Aug 2025, papers acknowledging IAM COMPACT already have 290 citations:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kikstra et al., 2022 (263) 	

EO# / EI#	Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact	Planned >	Achieved	Audience
			- Peters et al., 2023 (17) - Al Khourdajje et al., 2024 (7) - Stockhouse et al., 2024 (3)	
EI1	EC cites evidence from project outputs on the design of its post-2030 climate policy, including interactions with SDGs, and its post-pandemic responses (including in various EC dialogues, fora, and workshops organised by the EC).	N/A	Outside project duration	Policymakers in the EU, European scientific community.
EI2	No. of references to project outputs in IPCC AR7 and/or upcoming special reports.	30	Outside project duration	IAM community, Modelling networks and consortia.
EI2	No. of new scenarios submitted to IPCC AR7 and/or special reports.	≥200	Outside project duration	
EI2	Project acknowledgement in UNEP's Emissions Gap reports.	N/A	To be monitored in EGRs 2025-2026	
Policy-related reports, and non-scientific publications				
EO1	Policy briefs for EU & partner countries	10	11 (link)	Policymakers, Scientists/Researchers/ Academia.
EO1	Reports on national, regional & global mitigation pathways for the post-2030 period (D4.5; D4.6)	2	2	
EO1	Reports on sectoral & cross sectoral aspects (D4.7; D4.8)	2	2	
EO1	Reports on sub-national deep dives in Europe (D4.9; D4.10)	2	2	
EO1	Report on green recovery/Impact analysis of COVID-19 recovery strategies (D5.1)	1	2	
EO1	Reports on social & gender implications of Paris-compliant climate action (D5.2; D5.3)	2	2	
EO1	Reports on resilience against extraordinary extremes (D5.4; D5.5)	2	2	
EO1	Reports on social disruptive innovations & behavioural change (D5.6; D5.7)	2	2	
EO1	Reports on climate action & sustainable development (D5.8; D5.9)	2	2	
EO2	Reports on stakeholder co-created research questions (PRM) (D2.2; D2.3)	2	2	
EO2	Reports on transparent, multi-layer co-creation of the two cycles (PRM) (D2.4; D2.5)	2	2	
EO2	Reports translating policy needs into scenario frameworks (PRM) (D4.1; D4.2)	2	2	
EO2	Reports on orchestrating (MS4) and implementing innovative synergies with other projects (D3.10)	2	2	
EO3	Reports on open data management (D3.2; D3.3)	2	2	Modelling Community, SSH scientists, Policymakers (EU regional, national, local).
EO3	Reports on the open science protocols guiding the project (D3.6; D3.7)	2	2	
EO3	Reports on global and national sectoral drivers, barriers, and policies (MS5; D6.6)	2	2	
EO3	Reports on the two upgrades of I ² AM PARIS with new models, new features, and new workspaces (D3.8; D3.9)	2	2	
EO3	Report on a new set of model evaluation & diagnostics indicators (MS7)	1	1	

EO# / EI#	Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact	Planned >	Achieved	Audience
EO3	Policy catalogue shared with the modelling community in I2AM PARIS (MS9)	1	1	
EO3	Reports on interdisciplinary dialogue for modelling integration (D3.4; D3.5)	2	2	
EI4	No. of non-academic articles in the press reaching out to society	≥10	14	
	Scientific publications			
EO1	Scientific publications on national/regional & global post-2030 pathways considering extreme events, disruptive changes, societal innovations, gender, SDGs.	20	21	Scientific Community
EO2	Scientific publications on national & global mitigation pathways jointly produced with other research projects & non-consortium teams.	15	30	
EO3	Scientific papers on inter-/trans-disciplinary model science including SSH insights	≥12	13	
EO3	Consortium-wide scientific publications on inter-/trans-disciplinary model science including SSH insights.	≥10	13	
EO3	Scientific publications on interdisciplinary modelling science frameworks.	2	8	
EO3	Submissions to modelling consortia (IAMC, EMF, EMP-E, etc.) meetings	≥10	34	
EO3	Presence in conferences	≥25	50 (link)	
	Advancements to expand the modelling comfort zone and state-of-the-art in integrated assessments			
EO1	Report on a novel multi-model study framework (MS10)	1	1	IAM/modelling community. SSH scientists
EO3	New open modelling tools (D6.7; D6.8) & accompanying training material (MS6) for 4 non-high-income-countries.	7	7	
EO3	Climate-economy modellers and social scientists brought closer, using project's framework for inter- and trans-disciplinary model science including SSH insights in various projects	≥5	5+ projects (<i>ACCLIMATE, EU-CHINA BRIDGE, ENTICE, DIAMOND, TRANSIENCE</i>)	
EI3	Open national/regional models exploited by IAM teams after the project ends	≥10	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
EI4	Harmonisation & model integration/evaluation protocols established in modelling society.	N/A	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
	Stakeholder Database			
EO2	Total	2,000	5736	
EO2	No. of academia (at least 10%).	200	~500	All stakeholder groups.
EO2	No. of business (at least 10%).	200	~500	
EO2	No. of industry (at least 10%).	200	~500	
EO2	No. of civil society (at least 10%).	200	~500	
EO3	No. of modelling researchers.	200	~250	

EO# / EI#	Summary of the IAM COMPACT expected outcomes and impact	Planned >	Achieved	Audience
EO3	No. of social scientists.	100	~200	
EO3	No. of policymakers.	200	~2000	
EO3	No. of local stakeholders (modelling, ministry etc) from 4 non-high-income countries.	50	~50	
I²AM PARIS platform active support/exploitation and models documentation				
EO2	No. of modelling teams worldwide using the platform.	50	52	Modelling community.
EO2	No. of consortium models' documentation in non-technical language for all audiences.	25	25	All stakeholder groups.
EO2	No. of non-high income countries using modelling applications developed in the project.	4	4	
EO2	Level of increased confidence (satisfaction) in modelling results across members of the policy steering groups (satisfaction survey results at the beginning and the end of the project).	80%	<i>The process is in progress and the results will be reported in the final project report.</i>	Policy steering groups.
EO3	Increased understanding of modelling concepts among policy steering groups member (survey at the start and the end of the project).	50%		
EO3	No. of I ² AM PARIS workspaces with interdisciplinary insights (including from SSH).	5	8	All stakeholder groups.
EI4	No. of new workspaces explained in the I ² AM PARIS platform.	10	12	
EO3	No. of updates of the I ² AM PARIS platform with new models, new features, new workspaces.	2	2	
EI3	No. of Horizon projects supporting I ² AM PARIS platform's operation.	5	Currently 8 (ACCLIMATE, EU-CHINA BRIDGE, ENTICE, DIAMOND, TRANSIENCE, DECIPHER, IAM COMPACT, RETOOL), totally 11 (+ ENCLUDE, PARIS REINFORCE, NDC ASPECTS)	Scientific community (H2020 and Horizon EUROPE projects), IAM/modelling community.
EI3	No. of climate mitigation models supported by I ² AM PARIS.	70	62 (so far) (link)	
EI3	No. of IAM teams exploiting open national/regional models after the project ends.	10	<i>Outside project duration</i>	
External events				
EO2	No. of events jointly held in collaborations & synergies with other/sister research projects.	10	12	Modelling community, Policymakers, Industry decision-makers, Civil society.

4 Management of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan

The IAM COMPACT CDE plan operated as a cross-cutting framework, firmly embedded in key WPs' activities, thus shaped through the active contribution of all consortium partners. Each of them brought valuable insights from their respective project role, informing and strengthening the design and delivery of the planned CDE actions across all phases of the project.

To ensure clear planning and execution, CDE actions were treated individually, as separate streams in the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, anchored in the distinct purpose of each CDE core pillars⁹ - Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation - and tailored to fulfil a different aspect of the project's multifaceted outreach strategy, from sparking awareness and dialogue to securing long-term impact of the produced scientific results in both policy and society. However, together, they formed a coherent, purpose-driven pathway that powered the entire IAM COMPACT's CDE journey.

4.1 Communication strategy (M1-M36)

The IAM COMPACT communication strategy, launched from the project outset, defined our overall approach to public-facing communication, initially guided by a pedagogical vision to raise awareness and explain the project's research agenda through clear, accessible messaging. As the project progressed, it evolved into a more targeted stream of activity toward positioning IAM COMPACT as a well-recognised and trusted voice in the climate modelling landscape, supporting the dissemination and exploitation of the project results across key audiences.

4.1.1 Communication framework

Running alongside the project's "Listening" pillar, the IAM COMPACT communication strategy served to complement its activities and to strengthen the link with the broader engagement efforts, supporting and enhancing the Stakeholder Engagement Plan developed under Deliverable 2.1¹⁰.

Table 5. Summary of the IAM COMPACT communication strategy

Short summary of the communication strategy	
Goal(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness of IAM COMPACT and build up a close relationship with its multiple audiences. • Intensify communication with the IAM COMPACT primary stakeholder groups to gradually engage them in the project's activities. • Pave the way towards the implementation of the dissemination strategy.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop and update a dynamic strategy for the project's visibility and the overall CDE activities. • Establish a strong presence across multiple Social Media channels and 'teaming up' with Twitter/LinkedIn/Instagram climate personalities. • Networking and clustering activities with sister and other EU-funded projects under the same or relevant topics. • Motivating policymakers, industry representatives, and members of civil society (NGOs, climate activists, etc.) to join the core working groups guiding research.
Core messages	What is IAM COMPACT? Where is it going? What is in it for me?
Target audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General public/non-specialised stakeholders. • Non-specialised media and press outlets.
Secondary audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialised audience from across policymaking, modelling and the broader scientific domains.

⁹ [Sub-section 2.2.4](#) provides a deeper look into the three strategic pillars underpinning the IAM COMPACT CDE approach.

¹⁰ Deliverable 2.1 -Stakeholder engagement plan (D2.1) is available [here](#).

Right from the start, IAM COMPACT incorporated a suite of tools and activities to support its external communication efforts and connect with the broader public. At the core level, these included the following:

Table 6. Overview of the key communication tools and activities

Communication tools and activities		Short description
1	Visual identity of the project	Established under D1.1 ¹¹ , to standardise IAM COMPACT’s design language, ensuring a unified “look and feel” across all communication materials, making them easily recognisable and visually consistent. It includes the logo, colour palette, standard templates, and promotional materials (flyer, leaflet, poster, roll-up, PowerPoint presentation of the project).
2	The project website	Launched shortly after the project’s official kick-start it functions as the IAM COMPACT’s core public communication platform, sparking awareness, increasing visibility, and connecting with diverse audiences. Over the course of the project, it played a strategic role as dynamic hub for sharing progress, showcasing results, and promoting evidence-based dialogue around the project outputs.
3	Social Media (So.Me.) channels	From the beginning of the CDE planning process, the IAM COMPACT’s social media channels serve as key tools for bringing and maintaining the project and its achievements in the spotlight in a timely and accessible manner. Throughout the project, the CDE leader was responsible for running all So.Me. accounts and sustaining an active So.Me. presence, making sure that audiences remained engaged with all up-to-date project developments across all WPs and task activities.
4	Additional promotional material	Over the course of the project, additional promotional materials were produced, including (but not limited to) videos, infographics, newsletters and press releases, to further boost IAM COMPACT’s outreach. The latter were published regularly (at least monthly) to fuel a steady stream of fresh project updates, or on an ad hoc basis, yet strategically timed with important project milestones to enhance information sharing, visibility and impact.

Beyond its internally generated communication resources, IAM COMPACT tapped into a range of external avenues to expand its outreach, including among others partner-owned communication channels and networks as well as third-party websites aligned with the project’s research themes and topics. These efforts scaled up as project results unfolded, facilitating their widespread sharing across a larger audience in a strategic way.

Finally, a series of internal communication activities designed to support coordination and ensure alignment across the IAM COMPACT consortium, complemented our strategic communication planning. These mainly featured:

- monthly consortium meetings, held online, for progress monitoring and sharing updates on current work across all project activities,
- biannual General Assemblies, held in a hybrid format, providing high-level reflection on the ongoing project activities and forward planning, and
- targeted workshops, offering detailed insights into the project’s modelling tools and approaches, facilitating understanding, technical alignment, and collaboration both within the consortium and among key stakeholders.

¹¹ Deliverable 1.1 - IAM COMPACT visual identity & website (D1.1) is available [here](#).

4.1.2 Communication in action

With the communication strategy in place, IAM COMPACT moved from planning to action. This part of the report details how planned communication tools were applied in practice to build visibility and amplify IAM COMPACT’s presence across its full implementation timeline.

4.1.2.1 The IAM COMPACT visual identity

The IAM COMPACT visual identity is a collection of several design elements that serve to visually represent and build an easily identifiable appearance for the project, making it instantly recognisable and relevant among its target audience. Its essence lies in components like: (i) the project logo, (ii) the colour palette and (iii) a standard media kit featuring a set of ready-made promotional means and template layouts designed also for print. Consistency across all these “branding assets” helped create a cohesive, memorable look for all project-related outputs, supporting their lasting footprint well beyond the project’s duration.

In brief, the **IAM COMPACT logo** reflects the project’s multidimensional nature and scope through a clear and simple design.

Figure 2. The IAM COMPACT logo

Its consistent application and use across all project channels and materials was supported by a structured set of guidelines that also defined the project’s **colour palette**.

Figure 3. The IAM COMPACT colour palette

To spread IAM COMPACT’s identity across channels, a **standard media kit** was developed and made available for the consortium and publicly through the internal online communication system (SharePoint) and the website in respect ([link](#)). It features a set of ready-made promotional means designed to promote IAM COMPACT in key events hosted either by project partners or third-party entities and other aligned initiatives, as shown next:

- A **flyer** with high-level information about the project and the consortium, available in English and all partner languages.
- A **leaflet** with more in-depth content on project objectives, methods, and expected outcomes, targeting mainly academics, policy and decision-makers, and EU institutions - available also in English and all partner languages.

Figure 4. The IAM COMPACT flyer and leaflet

- A **poster** with content comparable to that of the flyer, yet flexible to accommodate project's ongoing developments, and adaptable for specific occasions.
- A portable **roll-up banner** for high-impact visibility at key events.

More on each of these standard communication tools can be found in the report D1.1 - IAM COMPACT visual identity & website.

IAM COMPACT

EXPANDING INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT MODELLING:
COMPREHENSIVE AND COMPREHENSIBLE SCIENCE
FOR SUSTAINABLE, CO-CREATED CLIMATE ACTION

IAM COMPACT supports the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, and the design of the next round of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and policy planning beyond 2030 for major emitters and non-high-income countries. It uses a diverse ensemble of models, tools, and insights from social sciences, integrating bodies of knowledge to co-create the research process and enhance transparency, robustness, and policy relevance.

The project explores the role of structural changes in major emitting sectors and of political, behaviour, and social aspects in mitigation. IAM COMPACT also quantifies factors promoting or hindering climate neutrality and accounts for extreme scenarios, to deliver a range of environmentally effective, viable, feasible, and desirable pathways. Finally, it develops technical capacity and promotes ownership in countries with limited in-house capabilities.

Contact Details
Project Coordinator - NTUA
Dr. Haris Doukas
Assoc. Prof., School of Electrical & Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens
Email: h.doukas@epu.ntua.gr

General Information:
contact@iam-compact.eu

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The IAM COMPACT project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101056306.

IAM COMPACT

EXPANDING INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT MODELLING:
COMPREHENSIVE AND COMPREHENSIBLE SCIENCE
FOR SUSTAINABLE, CO-CREATED CLIMATE ACTION

IAM COMPACT supports the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, and the design of the next round of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) and policy planning beyond 2030 for major emitters and non-high-income countries. It uses a diverse ensemble of models, tools, and insights from social sciences, integrating bodies of knowledge to co-create the research process and enhance transparency, robustness, and policy relevance.

The project explores the role of structural changes in major emitting sectors and of political, behaviour, and social aspects in mitigation. IAM COMPACT also quantifies factors promoting or hindering climate neutrality and accounts for extreme scenarios, to deliver a range of environmentally effective, viable, feasible, and desirable pathways. Finally, it develops technical capacity and promotes ownership in countries with limited in-house capabilities.

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Contact Details

Project Coordinator - NTUA
Dr. Haris Doukas
Assoc. Prof., School of Electrical & Computer Engineering, National Technical University of Athens
Email: h.doukas@epu.ntua.gr

General Information: contact@iam-compact.eu

www.iam-compact.eu

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Figure 5. The IAM COMPACT poster and roll-up banner

Beyond these, a **template IAM COMPACT presentation** was developed for direct use by partners at relevant outreach events, allowing context- and audience-specific updates and customisation.

Figure 6. The IAM COMPACT standard presentation

Finally, a **full set of ready-made layout templates** - covering deliverables, reports, presentations, newsletters, and press releases - were made available for direct use by consortium partners when creating publicity material on behalf of the project. From M18 onwards, an updated layout for policy briefs was introduced, complementing these tools.

Figure 7. Working documents templates

Of note, the IAM COMPACT website will remain active for up to four years after the end of project, ensuring long-term accessibility beyond the funding period.

4.1.2.3 Social Media channels

From its early days, IAM COMPACT has been very active on social media, prompting significant engagement on:

- **LinkedIn**, where the project’s official account (@IAM COMPACT) has built a targeted audience of 1,247 high-calibre professionals and peers from related EU-funded and other initiatives,
- **X (former Twitter)**, where the project’s official account (@iam_compact) has reached 709 followers, comprising a network of specialised stakeholders and influencing climate personalities, and
- **Instagram**, where the project’s official account (@iam_compact) has attracted 287 users from the general public, reflecting a steady engagement with wider audiences beyond the expert community.

Figure 9. The IAM COMPACT presence on SoMe

Posts were shared regularly, first on a two or three-day cycle per week, and after M18 posting frequency shifted to an updated and more targeted publishing schedule as presented in Table 7 below:

Table 7. Summary and progress of the IAM COMPACT SoMe strategy

SoMe channel	Aim	Initial plan	Updated plan	Status
LinkedIn	Increase IAM COMPACT’s visibility in the policymaking, modelling-research and scientific community.	3 posts/week	2 posts/week on current affairs and project’s progress.	304 posts 139k impressions
Twitter	Increase IAM COMPACT’s visibility in the policymaking, modelling-research and scientific community, targeting also civil society.	3 posts/week	bi-weekly posts on current affairs.	296 posts 60k impressions
Instagram	Increase IAM COMPACT’s visibility in the civil society.	2-3 posts/week	Ad hoc posts on project’s progress.	115 posts 10k views

Apart from building awareness around IAM COMPACT, the project’s social media strategy prioritised timely updates across all project activities bringing to light major developments from all WPs, from the launch of the IAM COMPACT website to flagship scientific publications and standout highlights from key events, such as conferences, policy-related events, modelling and capacity-building workshops, and core consortium meetings - most notably the General Assemblies. More than that, strategic posting paired with campaign-style content draw significant attention and amplified engagement across all So.Me. channels.

Up to nearly mid-2024, this type of content focused on key project milestones, including:

- the launch and first update of the IAM PARIS Platform
- the modelling capacity-building workshops in the four partner pilot countries
- the CWG’s activities within the first PRM modelling co-creation cycle
- the open-access models and the training pack stemming from capacity-building in Kenya, Ethiopia, and Sri Lanka.

As the project progressed, So.Me. activities reflected its rhythm covering highlights such as the release of the IAM COMPACT results validation and vetting app, the wrap-up of the two modelling PRM iterations, and the delivery of the policy briefs capturing the findings from the PRM-driven modelling studies. Looking ahead, upcoming efforts focus on promoting the relaunched, enhanced IAM PARIS platform and the final IAM COMPACT event, scheduled for August 29, 2025, in Athens.

Finally, beyond its core social media channels, IAM COMPACT also launched a YouTube channel ([@iam-compact](#)), adding another layer of engagement. To this day, it has reached 122 registered users and hosts 23 videos, 21 of which offer insights into IAM COMPACT’s modelling suite, and two on the issue of “loss and damage” and the project’s vetting tool. Together, these elements have collectively garnered over 5.2K views.

Figure 10. The IAM COMPACT presence on YouTube

4.1.2.4 Additional promotional material

Over the course of IAM COMPACT, an engaging mix of additional promotional material, including videos, infographics, newsletters, and press releases, was produced to enhance the project’s public-facing communication efforts. An updated detailed account of these outputs can be found in Deliverable D6.5 - Scientific & Policy Outreach (including briefs), available [here](#).

First, in terms of **videos**, IAM COMPACT has produced since the project’s launch:

- a series of 21 tutorial-style video content to introduce its modelling ensemble in a clear, user-friendly language,
- a podcast with leading climate activists, recorded on World Environment Day 2023, addressing the pressing issue of “loss and damage”, and
- a walk-through tutorial on the functionalities of the IAM COMPACT results validation and vetting app.

All videos are publicly available on the project’s [YouTube channel](#), whereas modelling tutorials featured also on the project’s website [here](#).

Additionally, 16 **infographics** were published on the project website ([here](#)) and SoMe channels. Among them:

- 9 offer concise, impactful messages on current climate and energy issues and trends,
- 1 demonstrates a brief timeline of landmark COPs, co-produced with Horizon Europe DIAMOND,
- 4 showcase expansion and development of technical and institutional capacity in the four case-study partner countries, and
- 1 illustrates the MEDUSA tool’s architecture and its potential linkages with Integrated Assessment Models.

Finally, a total of 14 **newsletters** and **press releases** have been issued until July 2025, starting from February 2023, as presented below:

Table 8. IAM COMPACT newsletter/press release distribution

	Month	Newsletter/Press release	Outreach achieved
1	February 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 1	Sent: 18/Open rate: 83.33%
2	March 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 2	Sent: 31/Open rate: 54.84%
3	May 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 3	Sent: 38/Open rate: 63.19%
4	May 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 1	Sent: 37/Open rate: 62.16%
5	June 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 2	Sent: 41/Open rate: 58.54%
6	July 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 4	Sent: 45/Open rate: 53.33%
7	September 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 5	Sent: 109/Open rate: 51.38%
8	September 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 3	Sent: 116/Open rate: 51.38%
9	October 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 6	Sent: 109/Open rate: 51.38%
10	November 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 4	Sent: 107/Open rate: 46.73%
11	December 2023	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 7	Sent: 106/Open rate: 46.23%
12	December 2023	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 5	Sent: 107/Open rate: 42.06%
13	January 2024	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 8	Sent: 107/Open rate: 46.23%
14	February 2024	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 9	Sent: 129/Open rate: 49.22%
15	March 2024	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 10	Sent: 144/Open rate: 46.15%
16	April 2024	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 6	Sent: 144/Open rate: 41.96%
17	May 2024	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 11	Sent: 145/Open rate: 50.69%
18	July 2024	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 7	Sent: 145/Open rate: 44.06%

19	October 2024	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 12	Sent: 145/Open rate: 49.65%
20	October 2024	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 8	Sent: 145/Open rate: 41.84%
21	December 2024	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 13	Sent: 107/Open rate: 46.73%
22	March 2025	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 9	Sent: 140/Open rate: 38.13%
23	March 2025	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 10	Sent: 139/Open rate: 31.16%
24	April 2025	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 11	Sent: 139/Open rate: 28.26%
25	May 2025	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 12	Sent: 138/Open rate: 36.96%
26	June 2025	IAM COMPACT Newsletter, Issue 14	Sent: 137/Open rate: 13.14%
27	July 2025	IAM COMPACT Press Release, Issue 13	Sent: 135/Open rate: 40.74%

Typically, newsletters issued monthly featuring all latest updates and noteworthy outcomes, upcoming activities, and other media-friendly content, while ad hoc editions support IAM COMPACT organised or co-hosted events to drive participation. Reporting back from high-impact events’ participation as well as project’s major milestones and flagship outputs, such as policy briefs or landmark peer-reviewed publications, are also shared via press releases. The most recent IAM COMPACT press release was issued in July 2025 to announce the project’s final event in Athens, while at least four additional releases are scheduled after August 2025. These new issues will ensure that the number of our recipients reaches - and probably exceeds - the target of 4,000 during the project.

Figure 11. Preview of July 2025 press release

4.1.2.5 External communication channels

In addition to its own communication channels, IAM COMPACT relied on a number of **third-party digital interfaces** to maximise its outreach impact. Beyond those of the consortium partners as well as references across aligned EU project platforms, the project strategically tapped into the mailing lists managed by IISD - notably the SDG News, Climate News, and Energy News as well as Africa Sustainable Development News and Asia Pacific Sustainable Development News, which offered targeted distribution avenues for sharing its updates. This effort proved especially effective in the closing stages of the project, significantly boosting the website traffic and enhancing the reach of the IAM COMPACT's policy outputs, particularly through the release of the final PRM-driven policy briefs.

4.1.2.6 Internal communication activities

IAM COMPACT's internal communication activities began with a two-day hybrid **kick-off meeting** held in M1 in Athens, where representatives from all 22 project partners reviewed and discussed the project scope, the activities workplan, their role in each WP, the modelling work, and the key steps to be taken to ensure the optimal delivery of the first-year outputs and milestones. In addition, starting in November 2022 onwards, IAM COMPACT held a series of **internal online workshop sessions**, to present the modelling methodologies assess their exploitable potential and co-develop meaningful approaches to stakeholder engagement. All sessions were shared internally and publicly through the project website and on YouTube.

Finally, to facilitate smooth internal coordination and streamlined exchange of project-related information within the IAM COMPACT consortium, a range of internal **communication channels and activities** were set up from the project's outset, as early as its kick-off meeting. In brief, these included:

- the launch of the internal SharePoint platform,
- weekly email briefings from the coordinator,
- monthly Executive Board (EB) remote meetings for progress tracking across all WPs and tasks, and
- biannual General Assemblies (GA) offering space for in-depth reflection and joint next-steps planning.

To date, a total of five GA meetings were organised, as reported below:

Table 9. GA meetings held since the project's kick-start

	GA meeting	Dates	Location
1	1st GA meeting	23-24/02/2023	Online
2	2nd GA meeting	28/08/2023	Mombasa, Kenya (hybrid)
3	3rd GA meeting	26-27/02/2024	Online
4	4th GA meeting	30/09-01/10 2024	Stockholm, Sweden (hybrid)
5	5th GA meeting	31/03-01/04/2025	London, United Kingdom (hybrid)

4.2 Dissemination strategy (M7-36)

Dissemination in IAM COMPACT is designed as the project’s long-term strategic effort to maximise the scientific, societal, and policy relevance of its key outputs, transforming their scientific insights into actionable knowledge for policymakers and peers in relevant fields. In doing so, it incorporates a set of more focused activities to support an ongoing dialogue and a growing knowledge ecosystem, with lasting impact.

4.2.1 Dissemination framework

The strategic planning and steps of our approach to dissemination are summarised below, in [Table 10](#).

Table 10. Summary of the IAM COMPACT dissemination strategy

Short summary of the dissemination strategy	
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target qualified stakeholders within the policymaking, modelling-research and scientific community. • Promote exchange and open dialogue between IAM COMPACT and the value chain stakeholders to co-create solutions and practices, produce demand-driven “system-level” impacts and potentially consolidate policy recommendations. • Implement means for making IAM COMPACT results and novelties available to all identified synergies and for showing expected scientific/policy/societal impact, in favour of their future exploitation.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous dissemination of results within the policy steering groups (of 3-5 policymakers/exercise) and core working groups (of 10-20 stakeholders/exercise). • Knowledge dissemination via: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ The IAM PARIS modelling platform, a vessel of the modelling community, in dedicated workspaces featuring inputs, outputs, explanations, visualisations, and model specs in technical and non-technical language. ✓ Scientific outreach activities, including inter alia scientific publications and special issues in high-impact journals and conferences, contribution to scientific assessments (IPCC reports), coordination with other projects, participation in the activities of EMF, IAMC, EMP-E, openmod, etc. • Keep updated the scientific community and policymakers, including capacity-building partner governments.
Core messages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IAM COMPACT fosters deeper cross-border, cross-disciplinary collaboration in IAM research and its application to policy. • IAM COMPACT lays the groundwork for shaping societally accepted, science-informed climate policy recommendations. • By engaging with like-minded projects, IAM COMPACT ensures its findings, tools, and lessons can inform socially responsive and practically viable policy pathways at European and global levels.
Target audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local, regional, national, and European policymakers and stakeholders. • Modelling communities and networks. • Academia/ Representatives of EU-funded project’s consortia. • Specialised/scientific media and press outlets. • European Commission (i.e., DG Research and Innovation, DG Energy).
Secondary audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry and business associations • Civil society, including general press and media outlets

From its initial planning, the IAM COMPACT dissemination strategy made use of a wide array of tailored tools and actions not only to raise awareness but also to meaningfully engage stakeholders in a two-way feedback process around the produced modelling assumptions and approaches. The goal was to actively ground the project’s modelling work in real-world perspectives, reinforcing high policy relevance and impact, which called for a cohesive, unified strategy linking the communication of the project’s scientific outputs with its stakeholder interaction processes.

[Table 11](#) that follows outlines the main dissemination means employed to advance this strategic effort.

Table 11. Overview of the key dissemination tools and activities

Dissemination tools and activities		Short description
1	The enhanced IAM PARIS modelling platform ¹²	The IAM PARIS modelling platform, originally developed as I ² AM PARIS under the H2020 PARIS REINFORCE project, and then evolved through successive EU H2020 projects, notably the NDC ASPECTS and ENCLUDE, was designed to enable input–output exchange among the global modelling community and other stakeholders. Under IAM COMPACT, the platform was further enhanced with additional models and policy tools to broaden its utility.
2	The PRM co-creation modelling cycles	Launched at the project’s start and ran throughout its duration, the PRM and its two co-creation modelling cycles brought together qualified stakeholders from various backgrounds in a collaborative open dialogue to shape the core priorities and directions of the IAM COMPACT modelling work. As the project drew to a close, PRM activities concluded, with the main results strategically disseminated through academic papers and targeted policy briefs.
3	Scientific and policy outreach through publications and participation in external events (scientific and non-scientific)	<p>As part of its dissemination strategy, IAM COMPACT used a diverse mix of scientific and non-scientific publications to bring key project insights to its core audience at all levels. In particular, over 35 scientific papers were planned to support the IPCC work and enriching the modelling community, along with over 15 public-facing pieces on climate, energy, biodiversity, and sustainability topics, targeting wider audiences via respected media and blogs across Europe and beyond.</p> <p>In addition, IAM COMPACT partners were encouraged to actively contribute to leading scientific and modelling conferences as well as relevant policy and public-facing events to spark dialogue around the project’s activities and outcomes, and foster wider societal involvement, thus reinforcing IAM COMPACT’s presence in the evolving European modelling and policy landscape.</p>
4	Enhancing networking and synergies ¹³	Throughout its duration, IAM COMPACT saw value in actively promoting synergies with scientific and policy-driven initiatives, including other EU projects, research consortia, and international modelling efforts. Serving as dynamic dissemination fora, these collaborations advanced the project’s policy and societal outreach and its ability to deliver policy-relevant outputs with wide stakeholder resonance.

To further support its core dissemination effort, IAM COMPACT integrated supplementary dissemination actions into its strategy. First, following the European Commission’s open access mandate, the project ensured unrestricted access to its results through open access journals and repositories, while consistently publishing project-related datasets in its dedicated Zenodo community. In parallel, it maintained a regular interaction with its Scientific Advisory Board (SAB), whose high-level external expertise and feedback were primarily channelled into the project’s policy outputs¹⁴ - most notably the IAM COMPACT policy briefs - strengthening their relevance and quality.

¹² More on the enhanced IAM PARIS and the final improvements made within the IAM COMPACT can be found in Deliverable 3.9 - I²AM PARIS v2.0 – Update (D3.9).

¹³ Details on the networking activities and the synergies developed within the IAM COMPACT are given in Deliverable 3.10 - Report on collaboration and synergies (D3.10), available [here](#).

¹⁴ While SAB’s participation in key consortium gatherings, such as the General Assemblies (GAs), was occasional mainly due to its members’ low availability at each time, their guidance enriched a range of project activities. Further details on how IAM COMPACT maintained a regular dialogue with the SAB members are provided in Deliverable 1.5 - Report on Project and SAB Meetings – Update 2 (D1.5).

4.2.2 Dissemination in action

4.2.2.1 The enhanced IAM PARIS modelling platform

Throughout its duration, IAM COMPACT undertook the enhancement of the I²AM PARIS modelling platform, originally developed under the [H2020 PARIS REINFORCE project](#), leading progressively to its recent relaunch as IAM PARIS. Just like its predecessor, IAM PARIS continues to operate as an open-source platform facilitating the exchange of modelling data in support of climate action through transparent access to IAMs, energy, and sectoral model documentation, as well as interactive result interfaces. Yet, its new version provides a more accessible, feature-rich experience for users from diverse fields exploring European climate policy modelling.

Figure 12. The IAM PARIS modelling platform

This evolution into a wider-reaching knowledge hub fostering collaboration across the modelling community and broader groups such as policymakers, researchers, and civil society is supported by six more complementary EU-funded projects, each contributing distinct features and applications - from national and sectoral model documentation (NDC ASPECTS), stakeholder-facing tools for industry mitigation data (TRANSIENCE) to citizen-led climate action (ENCLUDE), audience-specific outputs (DIAMOND) and customisable user interfaces (DECIPHER). Within IAM COMPACT, IAM PARIS was expanded in both content and functionalities - with extensive documentation for more than 60 global, national, and sectoral models and 12 scenario-specific workspaces to host outputs from the Policy Response Mechanism co-creation cycles, the capacity-building in the four case-study partner countries (Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine), and the model intercomparison exercises, prioritising open-source availability, coherent interlinkages across workspaces, and future capabilities for external users to create their own model profiles, documentation, and exercise workspaces. With these additions IAM PARIS is set to continue serving as a central Europe-wide and broader multi-modelling online tool for enhancing transparency and strengthen engagement in science-informed climate policymaking.

Figure 13. The Horizon Europe projects integrated into the IAM PARIS modelling platform

By the end of the project, IAM PARIS reached a total of 16,000 users, 11,000 of whom were gained in the period after M18. Despite a lower return rate, the bounce rate stood just above the ideal 50% mark- at 60%, resulting

in a solid user engagement, with more than 6,000 users navigating beyond a single page per visit. The reasons behind these inconveniences can be traced to the project’s strategic focus on expanding its outreach to new audience groups especially in its final phase, and partly to technical tracking limitations due to user privacy settings and anonymised browsing, as also seen with the project website¹⁵.

4.2.2.2 The PRM co-creation modelling cycles

Starting from June 2023, seven EU-level and one national Core Working Groups (CWGs) workshops were organised as part of the PRM operation, as shown next:

Table 12. Core working groups workshops

	Core Working Groups workshops	PRM cycle	Date	Link
1	Industry & Innovation (EU level)	1st	21 June 2023	Here
2	Optimal Transition (EU level)	1st	20 July 2023	Here
3	Global Effects (EU level)	1st	26 October 2023	Here
4	Behavioural Change (EU level)	1st	31 October 2023	Here
5	National Core Working Groups (India)	1st	6 November 2023	Here
6	EU Decarbonisation in the global economy (EU level)	2nd	28 November 2024	Here
7	Modelling the Clean Industrial Deal (EU level)	2nd	4 December 2024	Here
8	Citizens in the transition (EU level)	2nd	5 December 2024	Here

The scope and focus of each of these workshops, along with their contribution to shaping the IAM COMPACT’s core modelling agenda and priorities are detailed in Deliverable D6.5 - Scientific & Policy Outreach (including briefs), available [here](#). In short, within the two modelling PRM iterations, insights from the Policy Steering Groups were channelled into the CWGs workshops, leading to proposals for new modelling studies. The latter were finalised near the project’s end, with their findings disseminated through academic publications and policy briefs¹⁶.

4.2.2.3 Scientific and non-academic outreach

During its overall execution, IAM COMPACT exceeded expectations in both scientific and policy outreach, exhibiting a strong dissemination legacy. At first, the project’s **scientific impact** and contribution to the global climate modelling literature was notable, with a total of 51 peer-reviewed publications, one book chapter¹⁷, and over 50 conference outputs¹⁸, including papers, academic presentations and/or posters, and submissions to modelling consortia, all being delivered by July 2025. On the **public-facing front**, the project published 14 media articles in various public-facing outlets¹⁹, so enhancing visibility and accessibility of its work beyond the wider academic and modelling community. Again, towards raising awareness and informing a wider audience, IAM COMPACT participated in over 25 outreach events²⁰ overall, either external or (co-)hosted by the project.

A detailed account of all these outputs along with how they specifically contributed on the project’s long-term goals and expectations is available on [Deliverable 6.5 - Scientific and policy outreach \(including briefs\) \(D6.5\)](#). In brief, IAM COMPACT met and surpassed the set EO1, EO3, and EI4 relevant targets as presented in [Table 13](#) that follows:

¹⁵ See sub-section [4.1.2.2 -The IAM COMPACT website](#)

¹⁶ A PRM overview can be found on the website [here](#), whereas for cycle-specific details visit: first cycle [[here](#)], second cycle [[here](#)].

¹⁷ All the IAM COMPACT scientific publications are available on the website, [here](#).

¹⁸ All the IAM COMPACT conference outputs are available on the website, [here](#).

¹⁹ All the IAM COMPACT public-facing media articles are available on the website, [here](#).

²⁰ All the IAM COMPACT external and internally organised outreach events, are documented on the News/Events website section, [here](#).

Table 13. The IAM COMPACT scientific and policy outreach against the set long-term expectations

EOs	Scientific and public-facing outreach related targets	Planned	Achieved
EO1	Scientific publications on national/regional & global post-2030 pathways considering extreme events, disruptive changes, societal innovations, gender, SDGs.	20	21
EO3	Scientific papers on inter-/trans-disciplinary model science including SSH insights	≥12	13
EO3	Consortium-wide scientific inter-/trans-disciplinary publications including SSH insights.	≥10	13
EO3	Scientific publications on interdisciplinary modelling science frameworks.	2	8
EO3	Submissions to modelling consortia (IAMC, EMF, EMP-E, etc.) meetings	≥10	34
EO3	Presence in conferences	≥25	50
EI4	No. of non-academic articles in the press reaching out to society	≥10	14

4.2.2.4 Networking and synergies

Throughout its implementation, enhanced cooperation was central to the IAM COMPACT’s ambition to advance climate policy through joint workstreams within the European-wide and global IAM ecosystem. Overall, this is reflected in its in-depth, comprehensive modelling analyses of global and regional pledges, in the ongoing stakeholder dialogue within its PRM policy steering and core working groups interactions as well as in its work on the IAM PARIS open-access platform, through which the project aims to actively build links with the wider scientific and modelling community. Thereafter, this was translated into a strategic plan for fostering synergies and forming a robust network with a range of EU-funded research projects and beyond, laying the groundwork for an impactful collaboration with lasting value.

This strategy was put into action as part of Task 3.5 work, through which IAM COMPACT identified 23 related initiatives for potential collaboration— notably 10 within the same Horizon Europe cluster (CL5-2021-D1-01)— and engaged in a number of joint undertakings, ranging from cross-participation in advisory boards to co-organising outreach activities in the scientific, policy, and broader public-facing domains. The aim was to ensure knowledge and research results sharing among peers and other potential users beyond individual projects’ silos.

By July 2025, a total of 42 jointly produced **scientific outputs** emerged from these efforts, among which were 28 peer-reviewed publications co-authored with several EU-funded projects, such as PARIS REINFORCE, 4C, CONSTRAIN, ENGAGE, ELEVATE, ESM2025, GENIE, PRISMA, PROVIDE, TRANSCIENCE, and others as well as 14 joint conference submissions including collaborations with NDC APSECTS, ENCLUDE, and DIAMOND. All of them are listed on the project website, [here](#), and further detailed in Deliverable 3.10 - Report on collaboration and synergies (D3.10), available [here](#).

Over the same period, the project’s jointly achieved **policy and public-facing impact** was equally notable. Alongside its core co-creation activities, like the PRM interactions with key stakeholders and the capacity-building in the pilot partner countries, IAM COMPACT fostered its cross-project ties through shared participation in a series of policy events and workshops including the following:

Table 14. List of joint policy events and workshops

	Event	Type	Date	Location
1	Energy Modelling Platform for Africa (EMP-A) 2023	Workshop	April 11-28, 2023	Namibia University and online
2	Global Change Analysis Model (GCAM) Annual Meeting 2023	Workshop	June 6-8, 2023	Online
3	ICTP Joint Summer School on Modelling Tools for Sustainable Development	Workshop	July 3-14, 2023	ICTP and online
4	Summer School on Integrated Assessment Models	Workshop	July 3-7, 2023	Villa del Grumello (Como, Italy)

5	Climate Targets 2040: Bridging modelling and policy	Policy event	September 13, 2023	Bruegel (Brussels)
6	IAM COMPACT side-event at COP28	Policy event	December 4, 2023	Dubai (United Arab Emirates)
7	Modelling approaches to support Kenya's sustainable development	Workshop	February 12, 2024	Online
8	Annual PhD course: Advanced Energy Systems Analysis on the EnergyPLAN model	Workshop	April 22 - May 14, 2024	Aalborg University and online
9	ENCLUDE General Assembly	Policy event	May 23-24, 2024	Athens (Greece)
10	Energy Modelling Platform - Joint Global Training School 2024 (EMP-G)	Workshop	August 12-23, 2024	Trieste (Italy)
11	Clustering Event for Horizon Europe: Cluster 5 - Destination 1	Policy event	October 10, 2024	Online
12	Grantham Institute Climate Research Showcase 2025	Policy event/ workshop	January 22, 2025	Imperial College (London)
13	GCAM Modeling of European decarbonisation and EU policy strategies	Webinar	June 17, 2025	Online

4.2.2.5 Supporting tools and activities to strengthen dissemination outreach

In addition to its core dissemination toolbox as well as building on its commitment to impactful and transparent dissemination, IAM COMPACT actively adopted a strong Open Science approach - aligned with FAIR principles - to openly share its scientific and modelling outputs, enabling their long-term accessibility and usability. First and foremost, two open-access project-related communities were established on [Zenodo](#) and [GitHub](#) to support these efforts. In parallel, potential use of additional EU-wide open-access channels, such as the [Open Research Europe](#) and the [Horizon Results Platform](#), was also considered in that regard. Finally, regular exchanges with the members of the IAM COMPACT's Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) added a further important layer in our effort to strengthen the project's legacy.

Already from its outset, IAM COMPACT formed and worked closely with a high-level SAB, involving leading voices in the European-wide and broader dialogue for climate and sustainability. Continuous interaction with them through both fixed structures such as General Assemblies and scheduled progress reporting, as well as ad hoc meetings, provided valuable external insights complementing the consortium's expertise, ensuring further alignment with broader policy and scientific trends, and helping open-up new paths for project refinements and outreach. Accordingly, SAB-related activities were carefully managed under the project coordinator's guidance.

4.3 Exploitation strategy (M22-36)

In terms of IAM COMPACT, exploitation seeks to extend the reach and policy relevance of the project’s scientific and modelling outputs by further disseminating the body of knowledge generated across its work packages. To guide this effort, an early-stage exploitation roadmap was drafted at the project’s outset, revised in the second update of the IAM COMPACT CDE Plan, and then fine-tuned during the project’s last General Assembly to incorporate clear steps and targeted actions for sustained impact well beyond the project’s duration. The aim was to identify pathways for the project’s science-based insights to be effectively taken up and translated into practical support for EU and global climate policy landscape.

4.3.1 Exploitation framework

The strategic planning and steps of our approach to exploitation are summarised below, in [Table 15](#).

Table 15. Summary of the IAM COMPACT exploitation strategy

Short summary of the envisaged exploitation strategy	
Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitate the take-up and upscaling of the IAM COMPACT’s policy-relevant outputs among policy- and decision-makers, and other institutional stakeholders (external success). Leverage consortium expertise to inform and influence policy discourse through targeted dissemination and policy-facing communication channels (external success). Strengthen partners’ recognition within the climate modelling and policy landscape by boosting their scientific work’s visibility across high-impact scientific and policy platforms (internal success).
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Produce policy-oriented outputs, such as targeted policy briefs to inform climate research and evidence-based pathways in support of future action pledges of the EU and of other major emitting and non-high-income countries. Deliver tailored capacity-building and introducing advanced modelling tools for integrated assessments to strengthen policy planning and implementation in countries with limited institutional or technical capacity. Facilitate application of well-established models from the IAM COMPACT ensemble and co-creation of national-level models to address planning priorities within each case-study country.
Core messages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IAM COMPACT bridges cutting-edge modelling with real-world decision-making to support science-driven and evidence-informed climate policy formulation and implementation. IAM COMPACT’s modelling breakthroughs can serve as a catalyst for forward-looking, impactful climate policies across Europe and globally IAM COMPACT supports inclusive climate action by building long-term capabilities in emerging economies or countries with limited capacity, advancing both modelling proficiency and policy engagement.
Target audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policymakers and decision-makers at all levels. Modelling communities and networks. Academia/representatives of EU-funded project’s consortia. Specialised/scientific media and press outlets. European Commission (i.e., DG Research and Innovation, DG Energy).
Secondary audiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry and business associations Civil society actors General press and public-facing media outlets

With its first key exploitable results nearing delivery, IAM COMPACT complemented and strengthened its broader communication and dissemination framework through a set of focused activities designed to foster uptake by policymakers and integration into the wider scientific work. This served to ensure that robust modelling and analysis derived from the project’s research could directly inform climate-related decision-making, while being promoted through carefully aligned channels.

The key pathways adopted to deliver on this strategic direction are presented in [Table 16](#) that follows.

Table 16. Overview of the key exploitation tools and activities

Exploitation tools and activities		Short description
1	Policy-related outputs, including briefs and reports	From the outset, IAM COMPACT committed to delivering impactful, policy-focused outputs to clearly present its key findings along with their implications, and inform EU-wide and broader climate action. These included 10 policy briefs focused on future action pledges and long-term decarbonisation pathways for the EU, major emitters, and non-high-income countries, a policy catalogue to support the creation of multidimensional portfolio of policy measures, and 47 public deliverables capturing key outcomes from across the project's activities.
2	Capacity-building activities in the four case-study countries	<p>Capacity building in integrated assessment modelling, particularly in the four case-study partner countries, was central to IAM COMPACT's mission to foster ownership and sustained use of modelling tools in local decision-making processes. Through tailored workshops and hands-on training government representatives and modelling teams in Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine were supported in co-developing country-specific model applications to address local climate planning and priorities.</p> <p>IAM COMPACT's capacity building efforts in Kenya, Ethiopia, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine led also to the creation of standalone, open-access training resources, shaped through collaborative work with local experts and stakeholders in each case-study country. These resources complement the open-access modelling tools introduced through the workshop activities, providing also a solid foundation for long-term knowledge retention and application in support of evidence-based climate and energy planning in different geographical and policy contexts.</p>
4	Final EU conference	To maximise its policy impact, IAM COMPACT concluded with a final EU conference held at project close (M36) in Athens. Alongside sharing key project findings with its broad stakeholder network, including policymakers, modellers, and industry actors, the event featured a policy side-session to present and discuss modelling insights, policy recommendations, and the co-developed framework for expanded multi-model assessment, shaped through the PRM process. With over 150 qualified stakeholders attending, the IAM COMPACT conference is expected to drive broader recognition and use of the project's results across European climate policy agendas.

4.3.2 Exploitation in action

4.3.2.1 Policy-related outputs, including briefs and reports

As part to its commitment to maximise the real-world impact and relevance of its research, IAM COMPACT has produced a series of targeted outputs that reframe technical modelling insights into practical guidance for a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including policymakers, academia and researchers, and other societal actors engaged in sustainability transitions. These resources include a set of policy-oriented publications and technical reports that altogether aim to expand the project's knowledge footprint, fostering mutual understanding, international collaboration, and informed climate-related policy choices. In doing so, each of them contributes and directly supports the achievement of certain EOs and Eis, as described in [Section 3.2](#).

On the **policy front**, as of August 2025, 11 IAM COMPACT **policy briefs** aimed at bridging the gap between advanced modelling and actionable policy insights, were published²¹. Of them, five focused on advancing awareness of the PRM process and its co-produced outcomes, while one explored the trade-offs of alternative strategies for replacing Russian gas and their implications in terms of sustainability, affordability, and emissions.

²¹ All IAM COMPACT policy briefs are available on the website, [here](#).

Of note, one of PRM-related briefs was featured in the CORDIS Results Pack on Africa-EU collaboration.

Figure 14. Preview of the IAM COMPACT brief featured in the CORDIS Results Pack on Africa-EU collaboration

A brief overview of all IAM COMPACT policy briefs produced to date is presented in [Table 17](#) below, with further details included in Deliverable D6.5 - Scientific & Policy Outreach (including briefs), available [here](#).

Table 17. List of the IAM COMPACT policy briefs

Overview of the IAM COMPACT Policy briefs		Issue date
1	Stakeholder inclusion in climate and energy policy making - The IAM COMPACT Policy Response Mechanism	November, 2022
2	Three responses to the energy crisis - The co-benefits of energy efficiency	April, 2023
3	Cost of capital evolution effects on regional mitigation pathways: Financing renewable investments in low- and middle-income countries	March, 2025
4	Enhancing renewable energy system metrics: Security, flexibility and sustainability	April, 2025
5	Tech-constrained EU pathways to net zero: Impact of geopolitical disruptions and supply chain shocks	May, 2025
6	Collaborative modelling for new climate commitments	May, 2025
7	Sri Lanka's sustainable energy future: Insights from Climate, Land, Energy, Water systems (CLEWs) modelling	August, 2025
8	Sustainable restoration of the power and heat sectors in Ukraine: Implications for energy security and resilience	August, 2025
9	Pathways for sustainable energy transition in Kenya: Insights from Climate, Land, Energy, Water systems (CLEWs) modelling	August, 2025
10	Towards a just transition in the EU: The distributional effects of environmental policies	August, 2025
11	Energy transition trends in the European residential sector: Outlook for the EU-27 plus the UK by 2030 and 2050	August, 2025

In line with its roadmap towards policy outcomes and impact, IAM COMPACT developed a comprehensive online **policy catalogue**, emerged from the two consecutive rounds of stakeholder interactions within the first and second PRM cycles. From a technical perspective, the catalogue brings together data from the multiple PRM-driven modelling studies to provide a structured view of how the stakeholder-driven climate policy priorities were integrated into the IAM COMPACT’s model-based research, whereas its streamline interface equipped with flexible filtering options enables the intuitive navigation through a multidimensional portfolio of policy frameworks and the IAM COMPACT models that best represent them.

The IAM COMPACT policy catalogue is hosted on the IAM PARIS platform alongside models’ documentation and complementary data resources from IAM COMPACT and the EU-funded projects featured on the platform and is directly accessible via this [link](#).

Figure 15. Preview of the IAM COMPACT online policy catalogue

More details and update insights into the development methodology can be found in Deliverable 4.2 - From policy needs to scenario frameworks (D4.2), available [here](#).

Across its **technical work**, IAM COMPACT produced 47 comprehensive reports and reached 10 milestones, all capturing the full scope of its work and findings across each Work Package. With most of them being publicly available on the project website ([here](#)) and on Zenodo ([here](#)), IAM COMPACT formed a centralised repository of its technical and policy contributions, ensuring transparency, accessibility, and long-term usability for both scientific research and evidence-based decision-making.

4.3.2.2 Capacity-building activities in the four case-study countries

To strengthen ownership of science-informed policymaking and modelling in Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine, IAM COMPACT planned a series of **capacity-building activities** across the four countries.

In practice, starting from August 2023, three workshops were held in that regard, excluding Ukraine, where implementation proved difficult due to the ongoing war ([Table 18](#)). Each of them combined high-level conceptual overviews of key modelling concepts and approaches with practical, hands-on training in selected IAM COMPACT tools, enabling participants to develop country-specific, multi-sector model applications to inform their national planning and NDC-related policymaking²².

Table 18. Capacity-building workshops in the case-study countries

	Capacity-building workshop	Date of implementation	Link
1	Capacity-building workshop in Mombasa (Kenya)	August 29 – September 1, 2023	Here
			Here

²² Further details on the structure, thematic focus, and key results of all workshops are provided in Deliverable D6.5 - Scientific & Policy Outreach (including briefs), available [here](#).

2	Capacity-building workshop in Addis Ababa (Ethiopia)	January 23-24, 2024	Here
3	Capacity-building workshop in Mihintale (Sri Lanka)	January 30, 2024	Here
-	Capacity-building workshop in Ukraine	<i>Not implemented due to the war and security situation in the country.</i>	

Ahead of the three capacity-building workshops, a series of promotional activities were carried out. These included website announcements, direct email outreach from local organisers, newsletters and ad hoc press releases, and dedicated press coverage on local and national outlets, as in the case of Ethiopia²³. Custom visuals were created for each event, to support the outreach effort, offering additional visibility especially on So.Me.

Figure 16. Visual assets developed for the IAM COMPACT’s capacity-building workshops

To ensure continued and wider modelling knowledge transfer, IAM COMPACT delivered a full set of **open-access training and teaching material** co-developed during its workshops in Ethiopia, Kenya, and Sri Lanka - capturing context-specific insights for each case separately. Tailored for users with a technical background, these resources introduce key concepts, tools and approaches in integrated assessment and energy system modelling, and demonstrate practical applications of models from the IAM COMPACT ensemble and interconnected scenarios relevant not only to the case-study countries directly involved in the capacity-building activities, but also to broader planning and policy processes²⁴.

The IAM COMPACT material is freely available in Zenodo in the form of ready-to-use and editable .pptx files, and includes the following presentations (divided by concept):

- Introduction to energy (and electrification) modelling ([link](#))
- Introduction to OnSSET ([link](#))
- Minigrad modelling ([link](#))
- Use of energy system models and scenarios in policy - Case studies ([link](#))
- Introduction to input-output analysis ([link](#))
- Input-output analysis hands-on ([link](#))

²³ <https://www.esi-africa.com/news/kenya-climate-modelling-workshop-to-focus-on-key-energy-issues/>
<https://www.africa.com/iam-compact-a-horizon-europe-modelling-workshop-in-mombasa/>

²⁴ More information on the IAM COMPACT open-access training and teaching material can be found in the milestone report MS6 - Training material on concepts & tools, available [here](#).

- Energy-economy modelling case studies ([link](#))
- Integrated resource modelling and examples ([link](#))
- Designing scenarios ([link](#))

Since its first launch, the IAM COMPACT open-access training and teaching material attracted more than 2,000 online views and 920 downloads, reflecting a strong interest from the broader scientific and modelling community. A focused outreach activities, such as So.Me. posts, newsletter features, and email announcements to the IISDN discussion groups, actively supported by the IAM COMPACT partners, helped reach this result.

4.3.2.3 Final EU conference

IAM COMPACT concluded its work with a high-level public event at the Acropolis Museum in Athens, held on 29 August 2025 under the theme “Responsive Science in Support of Climate Policy Making”.

Figure 17. Social Media promotional visual for the IAM COMPACT final event

The event was co-organised by the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) and the Hellenic Society for the Environment and Cultural Heritage (ELLET) and marked the third in a series of conferences on Climate Change, Energy, and the Environment, following the earlier H2020 Paris Reinforce project editions in [2020](#) and [2022](#). Its agenda²⁵ featured five thematic sessions, each addressing a core challenge emerging from the evolving climate and energy policy landscape, ranging from how the EU can deliver on the Green Deal, while ensuring resilience and fairness, and Europe’s competitiveness in a time of global trade tensions, to Greece’s net-zero transition challenges and funding priorities, the broader implications of climate neutrality for biodiversity, resources, and land use and finally, the pathways to empowering the modelling-driven policy capacity in countries affected by crises and limited resources.

Presentations by project partners and external experts were complemented by panel discussions, ensuring audience engagement and a lively debate on pressing issues such as security and resilience in the EU energy system, lifestyle changes towards neutrality and sustainability, climate change impacts and needs in Greece,

²⁵ The event’s agenda can be found online ([here](#)) and in Annex 2 ([Figure 18](#)).

biodiversity and land-use management, as well as capacity-building in the IAM COMPACT case-study countries. Of note, the Mayor of Athens, also intervened with a keynote policy address underlining the city's commitment to climate action and resilience, reinforcing in that way the policy relevance of the multi-stakeholder dialogue that took place.

Through this two-way exchange between the IAM COMPACT consortium and the attendees, the event encapsulated the project's ethos of collaborative design and responsiveness to societal needs. This spirit was also highlighted through the presentation of the IAM COMPACT Policy Response Mechanism, which over the project's implementation period led to the co-creation of focused policy outputs with policymakers, industry actors, and civil society, ensuring that its research agenda remained close to actual policy challenges and priorities, thus resonant in today's complex and fast-changing policy landscape.

Overall, the project's final event provided a well-fitting closure to IAM COMPACT - one that reinforced its legacy in bridging science, policy, and society to enable a just and effective climate transition. It was attended by 153 stakeholders from across the local/national, and European levels, all representatives of policy, industry, academia, and civil society, reflecting a broad appeal of its theme and engagement. Targeted promotion through newsletters and press releases, partner outreach, and website and social media posts helped maximise the event's visibility, leading to 223 initial registrations before the event, plus over 30 on the day.

5 Operational guidelines

Implementation of the CDE activities within IAM COMPACT was designed as a resource-intensive and collaborative process, coordinated by the CDE leader (UPRC) while all partners contributed in ways most suited to their background expertise and capacities. To support this approach, the CDE plan provided a guiding framework to orient and stimulate proactive participation across the consortium, while maintaining consistency across all activities.

5.1 Coordination of IAM COMPACT CDE activities

UPRC, as the main CDE coordinator, was responsible for overseeing the implementation of the activities set out in the IAM COMPACT CDE plan. WP6 leader (KTH) actively supported all relevant activities, while final approval was granted by the Project Coordinator (NTUA).

5.2 Consortium-level obligations

While some partners (KTH, Bruegel, NTUA, WI) had direct roles in the CDE activities in line with their role in the project, all partners were encouraged and committed to regular participation by:

- communicating the IAM COMPACT research agenda to their respective networks, via their institutional website and/or their social media channels (if applicable),
- contributing to the content of the monthly newsletters/press releases or other relevant activities, such as public-facing publications, including (but not limited to) articles, commentaries, blog posts,
- disseminating the IAM COMPACT results through open-access peer-reviewed publications, active participation in scientific and policy conferences, forums and events, and contributions to open platforms,
- sharing information with the CDE plan coordinator, the WP leader and/or the project coordinator on relevant initiatives and events where IAM COMPACT could be represented, and
- when possible, reporting their communication and dissemination activities in the relevant Excel-based tool on the project's internal workspace.

5.3 Graphic identity and EU visibility

Unless the European Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, all communication and dissemination of results in any form - whether written or electronic - across all CDE tools and means were required to refer to and include:

Information on EU funding

Disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate)

As defined in Article 17 of the G.A.
The IAM COMPACT project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON EUROPE Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101056306.

It was also required to ensure the inclusion of the official IAM COMPACT logo and graphical elements, and to refer the project's website and social media accounts, when possible.

5.4 Publication procedures

Prior notice protocol | Unless agreed otherwise, any partner that intended to disseminate their results was required to give at least 15 days advance notice to the IAM COMPACT consortium, together with sufficient information on the results to be disseminated. In case of no notifications from other partners before the set date, the author(s) could assume that there were no objections to the publication. In all cases, confirmation of the right to publish was subject to the agreement of the project coordinator during the project lifetime, and openly thereafter.

Open access to scientific publications | IAM COMPACT partners were committed to publishing their scientific publications in open access, according to the “Gold” open access model, while publication of special issues was sought. According to the relevant project guidelines the “Green” open access model was also included, when applicable in case of e.g., institutional agreements. In all cases, the platform Sherpa/Romeo was suggested to be used to provide a summary of the permissions normally given as part of each publisher's copyright transfer agreement.

Furthermore, the IAM COMPACT considered submitting papers to [Open Research Europe](#), the open-access publishing platform for research stemming from Horizon EUROPE funding, while all project publications and accompanying data will be stored in the online project community created on Zenodo ([link](#)) and GitHub ([link](#)). All uploads were thus directly indexed in [OpenAIRE](#).

More details on the IAM COMPACT publication policies and protocols will be offered under Task 3.1 – “Exchange requirements specifications and data management” and its corresponding deliverables ([D3.2](#) and [D3.3](#) at the end of the project).

Open access to scientific data | IAM COMPACT collected relevant research data that were managed according to the Data Management Plan ([D3.2](#) and [D3.3](#) at the end of the project), in line with the FAIR principles and under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights. In the case of monographs and other long-text formats, the license could exclude commercial uses and derivative works.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) | The CDE activities in IAM COMPACT were deeply wedded with Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) protection, which was clearly stated in the Grant Agreement (Article 16 and Annex 5). In short, key elements relating to IPR included recognition of the overriding authority of the EC contract, specification of conditions of knowledge access and use, protocols, and plans for data collection in accordance with EU data policy, and specification of both excluded and required knowledge relevant to the project. In terms of ownership of new knowledge generated during the research, it could be transferred to the EC free of charge and without restriction on use/dissemination (Clause 29).

At the same time, unless published as a Special Issue of a scientific journal relevant to the scope of IAM COMPACT, the copyright of reports was with the IAM COMPACT consortium. Thereby, in the case of quoting texts, a proper reference to the report was needed to be made along internationally agreed lines.

5.5 Personal data collection and processing

Throughout all data collection activities, IAM COMPACT consortium partners adhered to the established EU Regulation (2016/679) on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data (GDPR). In this regard, they should guarantee that all personal data collected and/or analysed from the participating stakeholders was:

- processed lawfully and fairly, in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects and in a manner that ensured appropriate security,
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that was incompatible with those purposes,
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date in a form, which permitted the identification of data subjects for no longer than was necessary for the purposes for which the data was processed.

Accordingly, in order to ensure compliance, all personal data that were collected, was required be limited to information such as name, email, institution, stakeholder group, and country, and based on the owner's consent or option to change their mind and withdraw from the IAM COMPACT stakeholder database. Furthermore, IAM COMPACT focused first on the already established networks from the project partners' past and/or related activities/projects. In all cases, and where appropriate subject to regulatory constraints, restrictions, or licensing issues from the data owners, the data and their metadata descriptions were required to be anonymised.

6 Risk analysis and mitigation measures

Risks regarding the implementation of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan, and consequently the achievement of its expected objectives, were identified at the onset of the project and included in the Grant Agreement. They are presented next, together with their corresponding mitigation measures.

Table 19. Risk analysis according to the Grant Agreement.

Type of risk	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation measures
IAM COMPACT consortium partners' low contribution.	Low	High	Rigorous project management. Failure of individual participants will lead to an immediate assessment of capabilities and task reassignment. Partners have an adequate range of technical skills and can take over tasks if needed.
IAM COMPACT consortium partners' Delayed contribution to outputs.	Medium	Low	These actions refer to the internal adjustment of the tasks and have no impact on delays in submitting related deliverables to the Agency/EC. Even though, quality management, including early directions for timely outputs, and well-organised monthly calls (reviews/appropriate revisions) will ensure their effective implementation.
Low scientific and technical quality of IAM COMPACT deliverables.	Low	High	Rigorous quality management. First deliverable drafts are to be submitted one month prior to their deadline, for thorough internal review, including detailed feedback by Coordinator and 2-5 reviewers. All IAM COMPACT consortium partners have an excellent track record for scientific quality.
Lack of coordination with other actors and wrong expectations.	Low	Medium	Acknowledging challenges associated with the scientific paradigm to date and the requirement of inclusiveness in the climate dialogue, IAM COMPACT is oriented on co-creation with stakeholders (WP2).
Limited participation of external experts.	Medium	Low	Robust and rigorous CDE plan elaborated in Task 6.1, promoting project (outcomes) with all possible means. Besides that, to maximise participation, IAM COMPACT will use existing know-how in establishing an effective communication platform.
Difficulty in organising capacity development activities.	Low	Medium	It is foreseen that European partners can join planned webinars and workshops remotely and for that reason IAM COMPACT will use state-of-the-art tools in a highly efficient manner, to activate discussions and stakeholder feedback. Almost all IAM COMPACT consortium partners have relevant experience of the last 1.5 years.
Limited policy impact due to COVID-19 and delays to major policy or science processes.	Low	Medium	The general project planning fits well in the policy schedule. If COP sessions are further delayed (as with COP26) and GST or IPCC/other processes are affected, the envisaged impact is partly beyond the project duration. In addition, the COVID19 pandemic is seen as a "research opportunity" to use models in extreme/disruptive conditions.
Vulnerability of modelling to different types of uncertainty.	Low	Medium	Robustness of modelling is a core aim (multi-model inter-comparisons) of IAM COMPACT, with further enhancing the robustness of outcomes against uncertainties being one of the core IAM COMPACT WPs (WP5). Within it, the following activities are foreseen: (i) Pioneering new scenarios that better represent extremes, disruptive innovation, and behaviour changes in models, will be tested through

Type of risk	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation measures
			hindcasting on empirical data. (ii) A novel model inter-comparison framework will be developed.
Limited legitimacy of models, methods, and tools.	Low	High	Technical/policy briefs on model capacity are foreseen. Modelling activities will be carried out in an open access platform, and their specifications will be co-defined with policy/stakeholders, who will also drive modelling processes and co-develop modelling needs.
Limited contribution to major international scientific assessments (e.g., IPCC reports).	Low	Medium	IAM COMPACT consortium partners already participate in networks supporting assessments (IAMC, EMF, etc.). Among them, 11 partners are IPCC AR6 authors, while others participate in several project models that directly contribute to IPCC AR6. In addition, SAB features personalities with a remarkable track record in IPCC reports that can steer efforts to support climate dialogue.
Partners in conflict areas unable to perform due to the conflicts and/or particular geopolitical situation (e.g., invasion of Ukraine by Russia, etc.).	Medium	Medium	Online capacity development and training activities will be pursued with partners located in conflict or otherwise geopolitically sensitive areas if physical interactions are infeasible. The project will keep flexibility throughout its two co-creative cycles and shift capacity development and policy/scientific processes appropriately to ensure proper engagement of local stakeholders and overall implementation of the action with and in these countries. On the modelling side, consortium partners have collaborated in the past with these partners, so basic research infrastructure is already shared. More importantly, on the training side, international arenas can be used (e.g., EMP-A, and the Joint Summer School on Modelling Tools for Sustainable Development), avoiding conflict territory. Such arenas feature both training and a high-level political forum, allowing consortium, local analysts, and stakeholders to meet and progress. If tensions further escalate, self-learning material can be shared with, and online assistance is offered to, key analysts from the local teams.

7 Conclusion

Deliverable 6.3- IAM COMPACT CDE Plan (Update 2) marks the culmination of a comprehensive, evidence-based effort to design, implement, and refine a robust Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) strategy for IAM COMPACT tailored to its multidisciplinary objectives. Developed as a cross-cutting pillar under Work Package 6, the CDE strategy served well as an essential enabler of the IAM COMPACT's mission to inform and support the design and implementation of inclusive, co-created, and evidence-driven climate policy at multiple levels of governance, rather than just an ancillary function.

Over its three-year implementation, IAM COMPACT remained firmly committed to ensuring that its outputs - ranging from cutting-edge models and tools to policy insights and capacity-building resources - were not only technically sound but also accessible, relevant, and impactful. Its CDE plan turned this vision into practice through a dynamic, audience-tailored framework that was carefully designed both to align with the project's evolving priorities, and to engage with scientific, policy, and societal stakeholders alike.

An important dimension of the applied CDE approach was the blended use of standard and innovative outreach mechanisms. These included (but were not limited to) online platforms, including the project's website and So.Me. channels, infographics, blog posts and public-faced media, video tutorials, scientific publications and conference contributions, as well as participatory processes such as capacity-building workshops and co-creation modelling exercises in the four non-high-income pilot countries. The upgrade and active use of the IAM PARIS platform, alongside the project's Policy Response Mechanism (PRM), further facilitated stakeholder engagement and collaboration as well as knowledge exchange across geographical, disciplinary, and institutional boundaries. These two participatory avenues contributed directly to a set of policy-facing outputs, including policy briefs and a comprehensive policy catalogue, signalling the lasting project relevance in the future climate policy discourse.

The effectiveness of the entire effort is clearly demonstrated through the performance evaluation of the applied CDE strategy through a set of 11 predefined indicators. Achievements such as a widespread visibility, strong involvement of both expert and non-expert audience, and an early engagement with the IAM COMPACT methodological and modelling tools and outputs, all point to the plan's promised impact. Moreover, the inclusion of forward-looking monitoring benchmarks, particularly in areas such as policy uptake and global scientific and modelling cooperation, ensured that IAM COMPACT is on the right path towards shaping its legacy and establishing an ongoing climate policy dialogue with the potential to outlive beyond its lifetime. Notably, as of now, the project has achieved or even exceeded its measurable targets - current and long-term - which signals the efficacy of the adopted CDE framework.

Building on these results, we can contend that our CDE effort demonstrated its value by successfully contributing to the project's commitment to bridge advanced scientific insights with real-world stakeholder concerns, enhancing the transparency in integrated modelling, and augmenting the legitimacy and openness of climate policy development processes. Following the project's commitment to inclusivity and co-creation, the operational CDE model ultimately cultivated trust, broadened participation, and laid the groundwork for establishing IAM COMPACT as a benchmark at the science-policy interface.

Looking ahead, the legacy of the IAM COMPACT CDE plan rests on its adaptability and transferability, as well as its alignment with open science and stakeholder-driven research principles. These properties render it a relevant framework for future research initiatives addressing comparable cross-sectoral and systemic sustainability challenges. As this effort concludes, IAM COMPACT, together with the enormous scientific knowledge produced over its duration, leaves behind a strong evidence base and a proven pathway to long-term impact and continued relevance in shaping global climate action.

Annex 1. Messages (What/Why)

Table 20. Analysis of the key messages

	Key messages	IAM COMPACT will deliver	CDE objectives
1	<p>Under the Paris Agreement, Parties must pursue policies and measures to reduce GHG emissions, by preparing and implementing successive NDCs of increased ambition.</p> <p>Neither the first round of NDCs nor currently implemented climate policies are on track to meeting the Agreement's objectives while international cooperation in climate action remains limited.</p>	<p>Informed policy analysis to effectively support the assessment of global climate goals, progress, and feasibility space, by deploying a combination of appropriate modelling tools across fit-for-purpose scenarios.</p> <p>Comprehensive and comprehensible results and actionable policy recommendations on policy options to leverage drivers and overcome challenges to enhance mitigation ambitions, which can be owned by countries updating their NDCs and policy planning beyond 2030.</p>	<p>(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding</p>
2	<p>The modelling world has fallen short of its promise to include non-scientists/stakeholders in its activities, despite the need for wide societal and stakeholder support to underpin NDC design.</p>	<p>A collaborative process of knowledge creation that combines scientific and non-scientific bodies of knowledge and contributes to a holistic understanding of the climate-economy systems and interactions. Co-creation activities will be facilitated via the Policy Response Mechanism (PRM), a dynamic mechanism designed to make engagement user-friendly for all stakeholders, regardless of their experience in modelling work.</p> <p>At the same time I²AM PARIS modelling platform will serve as a central vessel for knowledge exchange among expert and non-expert audiences.</p>	<p>(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage</p>
3	<p>Non-high-income countries do not "own" their NDC commitments, as the modelling required for their NDC is often outsourced to consultancies.</p>	<p>A series of modelling capacity development workshops and novel modelling tools for integrated assessments in a selection of fast developing countries and large emitters (Ethiopia, Kenya, Sri Lanka, and Ukraine) with the aim to boost in-house capacities to scientifically underpin locally- and demand-driven policy formulation (including NDCs preparation) and broaden ownership on the country context.</p>	<p>(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage (iv) Ensure impact</p>
4	<p>Modelling usually focuses on the supply-side, despite the need to transform the demand-side and the high potential for behaviour and lifestyle changes.</p>	<p>A framing for complementing demand-side research with supply-side insights, by looking at the role of shifting lifestyle patterns and the societal acceptance in the decarbonisation potential and climate action. In doing so, IAM COMPACT expands its research agenda as to link policy/societal needs to modelling work and co-define with societal end-user those modelling requirements that are necessary for understanding the broader spectrum of feasibility and desirability of low-carbon transition and the key drivers towards this change.</p>	<p>(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage</p>

5	<p>Models for climate policy are mostly designed for long-term horizons and are not equipped to study deep uncertainties, structural changes, extreme events, and economic and climate shocks (such as COVID-19).</p>	<p>A novel integrated modelling framework based on a suite-of-model approach, to cover representative cases of a wider range of transition shocks and additional short-run dynamics, such as extremes, disruptive innovation, behaviour change, and sustainable development, which are typically underrepresented in the long-term scenarios design.</p> <p>This new approach accounts for a broader spectrum of uncertainties around the transition paths, providing a quantification of the range of likely effects over short-term horizons, which could encourage the use of such scenarios in policy work in support of the targets set out in the Paris Agreement and in the European “Fit-for-55” package.</p>	<p>(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Ensure impact</p>
6	<p>Climate action needs to be comprehensively assessed, by exploring the co-benefits of working across the broad spectrum of sustainable development.</p>	<p>A diversified portfolio of interlinked modelling tools comprising (sub-) national, regional, and global IAMs and sectoral models that altogether help explore multiple possible paths into the future, covering the large range of issues relevant to climate policy, like effort sharing under the Paris Agreement principles, and synergistic effects across policies corresponding to the different sustainability dimensions.</p>	<p>(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage</p>
7	<p>There is a need for a new interdisciplinary transitions research agenda that integrates modelling with social sciences, to assess the feasibility and desirability of the transition to net zero, not only in terms of what, but also of when, where, and especially for whom.</p>	<p>An interdisciplinary toolbox coupling IAM results with sectoral models, and modelling with uncertainty analysis tools, able to feed into robust science and policy prescriptions for policymakers to improve the accuracy and vigorousness of their narratives and eventually make more informed decisions considering multiple near-to-long-term scenarios.</p> <p>Robustness of modelling results is also enhanced by incorporating social, political, behaviour, and innovation aspects in models with insights from political and social sciences, providing granular and detailed information about barriers, impacts, drivers, and sequencing of transition.</p>	<p>(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage (iv) Ensure impact</p>

8	<p>New mitigation and sustainability pathways must be quantified and assessed against baselines, which are representative of real-world policy efforts and ambitions, and not against misleading or unrealistic no-policy/business-as-usual reference trajectories.</p>	<p>An expanded evaluation framework for benchmarking and validating the consistency and robustness of the modelling results based on multi-model diagnostic analyses (in complementary, cascading, interlinked, or inter-comparison settings) on the realism of post-2030 NDCs and long-term strategies against a multi-dimension set of diagnostics/evaluation indicators, including behaviour, innovation, sustainability, and social dimensions, allowing thus the investigation of uncertainty ranges instead of only sensitivities and observable trends.</p>	<p>(i) Raise awareness (ii) Generate understanding (iii) Engage (iv) Ensure impact</p>
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Table 21. Analysis of the planned CDE tools

Stakeholder groups <i>(high-level description)</i>	Internal Stakeholders	Policymakers (countries represented in IAM COMPACT)	Policymakers (selected non-high-income countries)	Policymakers (beyond the IAM COMPACT countries)	Scientist/Researchers/ Academia	Modelling consortia/ communities	Industry decision- makers/ Business associations	Civil society	Citizens	Press/Media
CDE Tools/Channels										
Internal communication channels	√									
IAM COMPACT website	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
I ² AM PARIS modelling platform	√	√	√	√	√	√	√			
Logo	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Flyer	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Leaflet	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Poster & Roll-up	√									
Standard project presentation	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Templates for working documents	√									
Social media (So.Me.)	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Infographics/Videos	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Commentaries, Newsletters/Press Releases	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Policy Response Mechanism (PRM) - Policy steering interactions	√	√	√	√		√				
Capacity-building workshops	√	√	√							
Open access self-learning material	√	√	√	√	√	√				
Non-scientific publications (blogposts, articles)	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

Policy briefs & Reports	√	√	√	√	√					
Non-scientific events	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√
Scientific publications	√				√	√				
Scientific conferences	√				√	√				
Synergies	√				√	√				
EU final conference	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

Table 22. The CDE plan's implementation agenda

The CDE plan timeframe – “Explaining” Pillar				
CDE strategy phases	Phase 1: Communication	Phase 2: Dissemination		Phase 3: Exploitation
<i>IAM COMPACT</i>	Preparatory stage	1 st Co-creative Cycle		2 nd Co-creative cycle
<i>CDE plan</i>	Initial awareness phase	Targeted dissemination phase		Presentation of results
Timing	Month 1-36	Month 7-36		Month 22-36
Methodological Pillars	Listening	Exchanging	Modelling	Expanding
WPs	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5
<i>WP objective</i>	Ensuring policy relevance and ownership	Open & FAIR science mutual learning	Quantitative evidence in support of post-2030 Paris-compliant climate action	Resilient, inclusive and sustainable recovery and development
<i>WP activities</i>	Operation of a PRM Co-creation of the research process and new knowledge. Engagement with policymakers in the EU and other countries. Scoping of policy and stakeholder needs Linking questions to the right models.	FAIR principles. Open protocols. Model coherence, comparability and consolidation. Harmonisation of input data sources. Coordinated scenario design. Open access to new code, papers and databases.	Diverse ensemble (global, regional, sub-/national and sectoral models). Detailed coverage of all sectors and their interlinkages. Multi-model runs & intercomparisons Post-2030 NDCs, (inter-) national scenarios.	Better real-world policy representation in models. Deep uncertainty & disruptive innovation. Holistic context of sustainability, including equity, biodiversity & biophysical limits. Behaviour change, social innovation, gender, sequencing of transition.
CDE plan activities	Raise awareness Generate understanding Incite engagement	Engage and ensure impact		Engage Maximise impact Ensure result's uptake

Annex 2. The final IAM COMPACT event

RESPONSIVE SCIENCE IN SUPPORT OF CLIMATE POLICYMAKING

Friday, August 29, 2025
Acropolis Museum, Athens, Greece

A G E N D A

09:30 – 10:00	Registrations, coffee, and get-together
10:00 – 10:30	Introductory remarks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the IAM COMPACT project (<i>Alexandros Nikas, National Technical University of Athens</i>) • A policy response mechanism for policy-relevant modelling science (<i>Ugne Keliauskaite, Bruegel</i>)
10:30 – 11:45	Delivering on the European Green Deal: EU-wide resilience, Member States, citizens, and justice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security, flexibility, and resilience in the EU (<i>Rasmus Magni Johannsen, Aalborg University</i>) • Aligning NECPs with the 'Fit for 55' targets (<i>Natasha Frilingou, National Technical University of Athens</i>) • Distributional impacts of EU climate policy (<i>Jon Sampedro, Basque Centre for Climate Change</i>) • Lifestyle changes towards net zero (<i>Gonzalo Parrado Hernandez, University of Valladolid</i>) • Panel discussion, including Q&A – Moderation by Yannis-Orestis Papadimitriou (<i>in.gr</i>)
11:45 – 13:00	Trade and industry: How can Europe remain competitive towards net zero? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU steel industry: offshoring, reshoring, and relocation (<i>Alexander Jülich, Wuppertal Institut</i>) • Renewable hydrogen trade in a global decarbonised energy system (<i>Shivika Mittal, CICERO</i>) • Geopolitically constrained pathways to carbon neutrality (<i>Eleftheria Zisarou, E3-Modelling S.A.</i>) • Understanding the trade-climate-industry nexus in a fragmenting world (<i>Maro Baka, E3-Modelling S.A.</i>) • Panel discussion, including Q&A – Moderation by Christina Tigka (<i>Inst. of Communication & Computer Systems</i>)
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch break
14:00 – 15:00	A deep dive into Greece's net zero transition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change impacts in Greece (<i>Gianna Kitsara, National Observatory of Athens</i>) • Greece's new NECP & funding requirements (<i>Dimitris Kollias, Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy</i>) • Towards a decarbonised built environment in Greece (<i>Nikolaos Kleanthis, University of Piraeus</i>) • Adaptation, resilience, environment, and national heritage (<i>Vasiliki Pougkakioti, ELLET</i>) • Panel discussion, including Q&A – Moderation by Thomas Doxiadis (<i>doxiadis+, ELLET</i>)
15:00 – 16:00	Climate action and broader sustainable development: trade-offs and co-benefits <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-sectoral mitigation and SDGs (<i>Konstantinos Koasidis, National Technical University of Athens</i>) • Biodiversity, material resources, & biophysical limits (<i>Theo Rouhette, Basque Centre for Climate Change</i>) • Land-use policies and renewable energy expansion (<i>Noelia Ferreras-Alonso, CARTIF</i>) • The impact of disruptive events in climate planning (<i>Alaa Al Khourdjaje, Imperial College London</i>) • Panel discussion, including Q&A – Moderation by Dimitra Spatharidou (<i>HOLISTIC S.A.</i>)
16:00 – 16:10	Policy Intervention: Haris Doukas, Mayor of Athens
16:10 – 16:50	Developing new technical capabilities in countries with limited domestic capacity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A novel framework for capacity development (<i>Francesco Gardumi, KTH Royal Institute of Technology</i>) • New energy modelling capacity in Ukraine amidst conflict (<i>Borys Dodonov, Kyiv School of Economics</i>) • Novel nexus modelling in recession-hit Sri Lanka (<i>Lahiru Theдавikum, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka</i>) • Whole-systems analysis amid polycrisis: Ethiopia (<i>Camilla Lo Giudice, KTH Royal Institute of Technology</i>) • Capacity building in Kenyan academia (<i>Francesco Gardumi, KTH Royal Institute of Technology</i>)
16:50 – 17:00	Conclusions

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the European Union

Figure 18. Preview of the agenda of the IAM COMPACT final event

Annex 3. Networking and synergies

Table 23. Indicative list of relevant EU funded research projects identified under D6.1 and D6.2

Project	Website	Partnership potential	Status	Contact partner
4C-CARBON	https://4c-carbon.eu/4c-project	Other relevancy	Ongoing	CICERO
AMPERE	https://ampere-euproject.eu/	Model enhancement for climate policy	Ongoing	
CAMPAIGNers	https://project.climate-campaigners.com/	Other relevancy	Ongoing	E3M, POLIMI
CDLinks	https://www.cd-links.org/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Closed	
Clima-Med	https://www.climamed.eu/	Other relevancy		NTUA
COMMIT	https://commitproject.eu/	Other relevancy	Closed	IMPERIAL, E3M
COP21 RIPPLES	https://cop21ripples.climatestrategies.org/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Closed	BRUEGEL
C-Track 50	https://www.c-track50.eu/	Other relevancy	Closed	NTUA
DIAMOND	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081179	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Open	E3M
DEEDS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776646	Other relevancy	Closed	E3M, KTH, UNIGE
ENCLUDE	https://encludeproject.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Ongoing	UPRC
ENGAGE	https://www.project-engage.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Ongoing	E3M, IIMA, THU
ENSYSTRAS	https://ensystra.eu	Other relevancy	Closed	AAU
FULFILL	https://fulfill-sufficiency.eu/	Other relevancy	Ongoing	POLIMI, WI
INNOPATHS	https://innopath.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Closed	E3M, Aalto
LOCOMOTION	https://www.locomotion-h2020.eu/	Model enhancement for climate policy	Ongoing	Uva, BC3, CARTIF
MAGICA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056920	Stakeholder dialogue/Capacity building	Ongoing	
MAIA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101056935	Model enhancement for climate policy	Ongoing	BC3
N4C	https://www.nature4cities.eu/the-n4c-project	Other relevancy	Closed	CARTIF
NAVIGATE	https://www.navigate-h2020.eu/	Model enhancement for climate policy	Ongoing	E3M, UNIGE
NDC ASPECTS	https://ndc-aspects.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Ongoing	WI, BC3, E3M, IIMA, THU, UMD
NEVERMORE	https://www.nevermore-horizon.eu/	Stakeholder dialogue/Capacity building	Ongoing	UVa
openENTRANCE	https://openentrance.eu/	Energy transitions EMP-E	Ongoing	
OpTIMUS	https://www.optimus-smartcity.eu/	Stakeholder dialogue/Capacity building	Closed	KTH
PARIS REINFORCE	https://paris-reinforce.eu/	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Closed	NTUA, BC3, BRUEGEL, IMPERIAL, CICERO
PLAN4RES	https://www.plan4res.eu/	EMP-E Other relevancy	Closed	IMPERIAL

Project	Website	Partnership potential	Status	Contact partner
REEEM	https://www.reeem.org/	Energy transitions	Closed	KTH, Aalto
		EMP-E		
REINVENT	https://www.reinvent-project.eu/	Other relevancy	Closed	WI
SENTINEL	https://sentinel.energy/	Energy transitions	Ongoing	AAU, UPRC
		EMP-E		
SPINE	http://www.spine-model.org/index.htm	EMP-E	Closed	KTH
		Other relevancy		
TIPPING+	https://tipping-plus.eu/home	Other relevancy	Ongoing	UPRC
WHY	https://www.why-h2020.eu/	EMP-E	Ongoing	E3M
		Other relevancy		
WorldTrans	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101081661	Integrated assessment to support climate policy	Ongoing	

Table 24. Indicative list of relevant networks and consortia identified under D6.1 and D6.2

Organisation	Website
ALLIANCES FOR CLIMATE ACTION	https://www.alliancesforclimateaction.org/
ALLIANCE FOR RURAL ELECTRIFICATION	https://www.ruralelec.org/
CARE-CLIMATE CHANGE & RESILIENCE INFORMATION CENTER	https://careclimatechange.org/
CCG-CLIMATE COMPATIBLE GROWTH	https://climatecompatiblegrowth.com/
CENII-EU GCC CLEAN ENERGY NETWORK II	https://www.ceps.eu/ceps-projects/eu-gcc-clean-energy-network-ii-cenii/
CEPS-CENTER OF EUROPEAN POLICY STUDIES	https://www.ceps.eu/
CLIMA-CENTER FOR CLIMATE RISK MANAGEMENT	https://www.clima.psu.edu/
CLIMATE ALLIANCE	https://www.climatealliance.org/home.html
CLIMATE REALITY	climaterealityproject.org
COMMUNITY ENERGY FOR ENERGY SOLIDARITY	https://www.energysolidarity.eu/
COP 21 RIPPLES	https://cop21ripples.climatestrategies.org/
EAPN-EUROPEAN ANTI-POVERTY NETWORK	https://www.eapn.eu/
EAUC-THE ALLIANCE FOR SUSTAINABILITY LEADERSHIP IN EDUCATION	https://www.eauc.org.uk/home
ECEMF-EUROPEAN CLIMATE & ENERGY MODELING FORUM	https://www.ecemf.eu/
EEG-ENERGY & ECONOMIC GROWTH Applied Research Program	https://www.energyeconomicgrowth.org/
ELARD-EUROPEAN LEADER ASSOCIATION FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT	http://elard.eu/
EMF-ENERGY MODELING FORUM	https://emf.stanford.edu/
EMP-E ENERGY MODELLING PLATFORM FOR EUROPE	https://www.energymodellingplatform.eu/
ENERGIZE Co2MMUNITY	https://co2mmunity.eu/
ENERGY CITIES	https://energy-cities.eu/
ENGAGER-ENERGY POVERTY ACTION: AGENDA Co-CREATION & KNOWLEDGE INNOVATION	https://www.engager-energy.net/
EPAH-ENERGY POVERTY ADVISORY HUB	https://energy-poverty.ec.europa.eu/index_en
EURO CITIES	https://eurocities.eu/
EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION FOR INNOVATION IN LOCAL DEVELOPMENT	https://www.aeidl.eu/
EUROPEAN CLIMATE PACT	https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/european-green-deal/european-climate-pact_en
EUROPEAN RURAL DEVELOPMENT NETWORK	http://erdn.eu/

FREE INITIATIVE	https://www.rural-energy.eu/
GCCA-THE GLOBAL CLIMATE CHANGE ALLIANCE PLUS	https://www.gcca.eu/
	https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/gcca-community
GCP-GLOBAL CARBON PROJECT	https://www.globalcarbonproject.org/
HYDROGEN EUROPE	https://hydrogeneurope.eu/
IAMC-INTEGRATED ASSESMENT MODELING CONSORTIUM	https://www.iamconsortium.org/
IEA-WEO	
IEPAW-INTERNATIONAL ENERGY POVERTY ACTION WEEK	https://www.energy-poverty-action.org/
IFLS-INSTITUTE FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH	https://www.ifls.de/en/
IPCC-INTERGOVERNMENTAL PANEL ON CLIMATE CHANGE	https://www.ipcc.ch/
OPENMOD-OPEN ENERGY MONDELLING INITIATIVE	https://openmod-initiative.org/
PCHES -PROGRAM ON COUPLED HUMAN & EARTH SYSTEMS	https://www.pches.psu.edu/
PIAMDDI-PROGRAM ON INTEGRATED ASSESSMENT MODEL DEVELOPMENT, DIAGNOSTICS & INTER-COMPARISON	https://www.pches.psu.edu/iamddi/
RedMENTES	https://redmentes.es/
RENOVATE EUROPE	https://www.renovate-europe.eu/
RIGHT TO ENERGY COALITION	https://righttoenergy.org/
RURAL ENERGY COMMUNITY ADVISORY HUB	https://rural-energy-community-hub.ec.europa.eu/index_en
STRN-SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITIONS RESEARCH NETWORK	https://transitionsnetwork.org/
UN CLIMATE CHANGE	unfccc.int
UN ENVIRONMENT PROGRAMME	unep.org
WCRP-WORLD CLIMATE RESEARCH PROGRAM	https://www.wcrp-climate.org/wgcm-cmip/wgcm-cmip6

Table 25. Online collaboration platforms identified under D6.1 and D6.2

Online collaboration platforms	Website link
Capacity4Dev	https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/
Climatechangemitigation.eu	http://climatechangemitigation.eu/
Climate-ADAPT	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/
IISD SDG Knowledge Hub	http://sdg.iisd.org/

Annex 4. Scientific and non-scientific events

Table 26. Indicative list of relevant scientific and non-scientific events mapped under D6.1 and D6.2

Event	Link	Level
4th European Conference Hydrogen & P2X 2023	https://fortesmedia.com/hydrogen-p2x-2023,4,en,2,1,22.html	EU
6th Annual World Congress of Smart Materials-2023	https://www.bitcongress.com/topwscsm2023/WelcomeMessage.aspx	International
7th Edition of Global Energy Meet	https://globalenergymeet.com/	International
AIAI 2023: 19th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations	https://ifipaiai.org/2023/	EU
AIEE Energy Symposium	https://www.aieesymposium.eu/	EU
AIEE 4th International Conference	http://www.aiee.net/	International
ACEEE-Industry Summer Study	https://www.aceee.org/2023-industry-summer-study	International
Alliance to Save Energy EE Global	https://eeglobalalliance.org/ee-global-forum	International
BECC-Behavior, Energy & Climate Change Conference	https://becccconference.org/	International
Berliner Energietage	https://www.energietage.de/home.html	National
Berlin Green Investment Summit	https://wermutham.com/berlin-green-investment-summit-agenda/	National
C4E Forum	https://c4eforum.net/	International
CBA17-Conference on Community-Based Adaptation to Climate Change	https://www.globalresiliencepartnership.org/event/cba17-local-solutions-inspiring-global-action/	International
Cities Forum 2023-Together for green & just cities	https://www.uia-initiative.eu/en/events/cities-forum-2023-together-green-and-just-cities	EU
City Energy Conference 2023	https://eu-mayors.ec.europa.eu/en/node/538	EU
CO2 Capture & Reuse	https://fortesmedia.com/co2-capture-storage-reuse-2023,4,en,2,1,21.html	EU
CoEEE2023-International Joint Conference on Energy & Environmental Engineering	https://www.coeee.org/	International
Construmat-Building Sustainability	https://www.construmat.com/en/	EU
EasyChair Smart CFP (Archive)	https://easychair.org/cfp/	International
ECEEE -Summer Study	https://www.eceee.org/events/eceee-summer-studies/	EU
ECEMP-European Climate & Energy Modeling Platform Conferences	https://www.energymodellingplatform.eu/	EU
ECRES - European Conference on Renewable Energy Systems 2023	https://www.ecres.net/	EU
EREE 2023-5th International Conference on Environment, Resources & Energy Engineering	http://www.eree.org/	International
ESCC-International Conference on Energy, Sustainability & Climate Crisis	http://escc.uth.gr/	International
Ecomondo - The Green Technology Expo	https://www.ecomondo.com/	National
Energy Modeling Forum (EMF) events	https://emf.stanford.edu/all-events	International

Energy Efficiency Finance Forum	https://www.aceee.org/2022-energy-efficiency-finance-forum	International
Energy and Sustainability 2023-10th International Conference	https://www.wessex.ac.uk/conferences/2023/energy-and-sustainability-2023	International
Energy Transition Summit 2023	https://marketforcelive.com/future-of-utilities/events/energy-transition-summit/?gclid=Cj0KCQjAiJSeBhCCARIsAHnAzT8rU1Wqee58m-oXfQeuCu-ekUPqTizGRW8CFcGoCjXJH80juhvHumkaAmn7EALw_wcB	EU
EnergyTECH 2023: Renewable Energy, Resources and Sustainable Technologies	https://energytechconference.com/	International
ENLIT Europe	https://www.enlit-europe.com/	EU
EMC-Eastern Mediterranean Conference & Exhibition	https://emc-cyprus.com/#about	EU
EU Conference on modelling for policy support	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/event/2021-eu-conference-modelling-policy-support-collaborating-across-disciplines-tackle-key_en	EU
Eu-SPRI Annual Conference	https://www.euspri2023.com/	EU
EURO 33rd Conference	https://euro2024cph.dk/	EU
EURO events	https://www.euro-online.org/web/pages/100/conferences	EU
European Energy Transition Conference	https://www.climate-chance.org/en/event-calendar/2023-european-energy-transition-conference/	EU
European Hydrogen Week	http://www.eurohydrogenweek.eu	EU
EUSEW-European Sustainable Energy Week	https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/	EU
EU-SPRI Annual Conference	https://www.euspri2023.com/	EU
ESEE (European Society for Ecological Economics) events	https://ecolecon.eu/category/events/upcoming-events/	EU
FLEXCON-Cocreate Flexible Energy	https://flexcon2022.eu/about/	International
FLINS/ISKE 2023	https://flins2022.scievent.com/	International
Forum on Scenarios for Climate and Societal Futures	https://scenariosforum.org/	EU
GEET-Green Energy & Environmental Technology International Conference	https://greenenergy-europe.eu/	International
Green Finance Research Advances Conference	https://green-finance-research-advances-2022.org/	EU
HAEE events	https://www.haee.gr/conferences-and-events/haee-events/	EU
IAMC Annual Meeting	https://www.iamconsortium.org/events/category/annual-meeting-of-the-iamc/	International
IAEE 44th International Conference	https://iaee2023.saudi-ae.sa/	International
IAEE 18th European Conference	https://www.iaee.org/en/conferences/europe.aspx	EU
ICEECC 2023: 17th International Conference on Energy, Environment & Climate Change	https://waset.org/energy-environment-and-climate-change-conference-in-march-2023-in-bangkok	International
ICEES 2023-7th International Conference on Energy and Environmental Science	http://www.icees.org/	International
ICEESEN-International Conference on Energy, Environment & Storage of Energy	https://iceesen.com/	International

ICFEE 2023-13th International Conference on Future Environment and Energy	http://www.icfee.org/	International
IEPAW-International Energy Poverty Action Week	https://www.energy-poverty-action.org/	International
ICEEEP 2023: 7th International Conference on Energy Economics & Energy Policy	http://www.iceeep.com/	International
ICEDRD 2023: 17. International Conference on Environmental Design and Rural Development	https://waset.org/environmental-design-and-rural-development-conference-in-may-2023-in-rome	International
IISA 2023: 14th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems & Applications	https://easyconferences.eu/iisa2023/	International
Island Finance Forum 2023: Investment for Sustainable Development	https://islandinnovation.co/events/island-finance-forum/?utm_source=sendinblue&utm_campaign=II136%20-%20Island%20Innovation%20Newsletter%2005012023&utm_medium=email	EU
Joint EASST/4S conference	https://www.4sonline.org/meeting/future-meetings/	International
Lisbon Energy Summit & Exhibition	https://www.lisbonenergysummit.com/?utm_source=google&utm_medium=cpc&utm_campaign=launch&qclid=Cj0KCCQiAjJSeBhCCARIsAHnAzT_rYwK9Dk8ffoCWnMgsDHt74B65PSN3IcbJv10Nt2WOIwdRkAaMO1QaAqaPEALw_wcB	International
REDay-Renovate Europe Day	https://www.renovate-europe.eu/	EU
RenewableEng-International Conference on Renewable & Sustainable Energy	https://xpertsmeetings.org/renewableeng23/	International
Right to Energy Forum 2023	https://righttoenergy.org/forum-2023/	EU
SCEW 2023: Smart City Expo World Congress	https://www.smartcityexpo.com/	International
SETAC Europe 33rd Annual Meeting	https://europe2023.setac.org/	EU
SEEP 2023- 15th International Conference on Sustainable Energy & Environmental Protection	https://seepconference.com/	International
SCORAI-ERCP WUR Conference: Transforming consumption-production systems towards just & sustainable futures	https://www.scp-conference-2023.com/web	EU
SCORAI-ERCP WUR Conference: Session " The Wellbeing Economy: Pathway to Consumption Sufficiency and a Post-Growth Economy?"	https://www.eceee.org/events/calendar/event/clone-abstracts-deadline-the-wellbeing-economy-pathway-to-consumption-sufficiency-and-a-post-growth-economy/	EU
SDEWES 18th Conference (Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems)	https://www.dubrovnik2023.sdewes.org/	EU
SEED Conference-International Conference on the Sustainable Energy & Environmental Development	https://www.leedsbeckett.ac.uk/events/conferences/seeds-conference-2022/	International
Smart 2023: 10th ECCOMAS Thematic Conference on Smart Structures and Materials	https://www.smart2023.eu/	EU

Smart Cities Conferences 2023/2024/2025	https://conferenceindex.org/conferences/smart-cities	International
Smart Greens 2023: 12th International Conference on Smart Cities & Green ICT Systems	https://smartgreens.scitevents.org/	International
The JRC events/workshops	https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/event/FutureEvents	International
The International Society for Ecological Modelling (ISEM) Global Conference 2023: Ecological Models for Tomorrow's Solutions	https://www.elsevier.com/events/conferences/international-society-for-ecological-modelling-global-conference?utm_campaign=STMJ_1666267551_CONF_NEWS_AB&utm_medium=email&utm_source=Medlist&dgcid=STMJ_1666267551_CONF_NEWS_AB	International
UN climate change conference (COP28)	https://unfccc.int/	International
VIS 2023-Virtual Island Summit	https://islandinnovation.co/events/virtual-island-summit/	EU
WASET-World Academy of Science, Engineering & Technology (Archive)	https://waset.org/energy-conferences-in-2023	International
World Conference on Climate & Sustainability (Climate Week 2023)	https://climateweek.thepeopleevents.com/	International
World Green Building Week	https://worldgbc.org/	International
WSEC-World Smart City Expo	https://www.worldsmartcityexpo.com/fairDash.do?hl=ENG	International
WSED-World Sustainable Energy Days	https://www.wsed.at/	International

Annex 5. News and Media websites

Table 27. Indicative list of leading news and media channels mapped under D6.1 and D6.2

News and Media Channels	Website link
EC Website (CORDIS)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223239/factsheet/en
Research and Innovation Success Stories	https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/success-stories
EURACTIV	https://www.euractiv.com/
The Conversation	https://theconversation.com/
ClimateChangePost	https://www.climatechangepost.com/
The Guardian	https://www.theguardian.com/
Research*eu	https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/home_en.html
HORIZON magazine	https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine
The Beam	https://the-beam.com/